

Maren Charlott Viktoria Fuglås

Comparing PFAS concentrations in non-functional recycled and post-consumer textiles: Implications for a toxic-free circular economy

Master's thesis in Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry

Supervisor: Hans Peter Arp

Co-supervisor: Anna Lennquist and Alexandros Asimakopoulos

May 2023

Maren Charlott Viktoria Fuglås

Comparing PFAS concentrations in non-functional recycled and post-consumer textiles: Implications for a toxic-free circular economy

Master's thesis in Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry
Supervisor: Hans Peter Arp
Co-supervisor: Anna Lennquist and Alexandros Asimakopoulos
May 2023

Norwegian University of Science and Technology
Faculty of Natural Sciences
Department of Chemistry

Abstract

The presence of Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in textiles is considered an obstacle to achieving non-toxic material cycles in the desire of increasing recycling rates for textiles under the EU's Circular Economy Action Plan, a part of EU's Green Deal. PFAS are very persistent, mobile, and toxic substances that are heavily used in textile production through finishing processes to achieve water-, oil-, and, stain-repellence in functional textiles. These types of functional textiles are not conveniently recycled, so the recycling potential lies in non-functional textiles. A concern however is that PFAS still might be present in these types of textiles through contamination by processing aids used during textile manufacturing, or by environmental or human interference in the use-phase. PFAS levels could then accumulate in recycled textiles when subject to mechanical recycling which has been shown for other types of materials. This study analyzed textiles from two points of the circular supply chain: rejected post-consumer textiles collected from Fretex (n=30) and newly purchased textiles made fully or partly from recycled materials (n=37) by targeted PFAS analysis using Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography coupled with Electrospray Ionisation and Triple Quadruple Mass Spectrometry. A method test of two different protocols for the extraction of solid samples was executed. The protocol using methanol as extraction solvent showed better performance characteristics in regards to recoveries and matrix effects, and was used for the sample preparation of the textile samples. The samples were washed prior to extraction, and 10 samples of this water was also subject to targeted PFAS analysis. 96% of the textile samples had at least one detection of a target PFAS, and PFOS was the most detected target PFAS. Concentrations of total PFAS for all samples ranged from 0.05-98.29 ng/g and 0.001 - 3.338 ng/cm². Median total PFAS values for post-consumer textiles (16.82 ng/g, 0.379 ng/cm²) were higher than for recycled textiles (3.32 ng/g, 0.181 ng/cm²). Short-chain PFCAs had the highest contribution in the composition of PFAS in recycled textiles, whilst long-chain PFSAs contributed the most the composition of PFAS to post-consumer textiles. Synthetic materials contained substantially higher concentrations of short-chain PFCAs and "other PFAS", but a general trend for all PFAS groups was not observed. All water samples obtained from washing of the textile samples had detections of at least one target PFAS, and diSAMPAP was detected in all. 3 samples exceeded the EU's regulatory limits for PFOS, but no samples exceeded the limits for PFOA.

Sammendrag

Tilstedeværelse av per- og polyfluoralkylstoffer (PFAS) i tekstiler regnes som en hinder for å oppnå materialsykluser fri for miljøgifter under ønsket om å øke resirkuleringsraten for tekstiler under EU's handlingsplan for sirkulær økonomi, en del av EU's Grønne Giv. PFAS er svært persistente, mobile og giftige stoffer som er mye brukt i tekstilproduksjon gjennom etterbehandlingsprosesser for å oppnå vann-, olje- og flekkavstøtende egenskaper i funksjonelle tekstiler. Slike funksjonelle tekstiler er det ikke lett å resirkulere, så resirkuleringspotensialet ligger i ikke-funksjonelle tekstiler. En bekymring er imidlertid at PFAS også kan være tilstede i denne typen av tekstiler grunnet kontaminering fra prosesseringshjelpemidler der PFAS er tilsatt som brukes under tekstilproduksjon, eller av miljømessig eller menneskelig innblanding i bruksfasen. Nivåene av PFAS kan da akkumulere i resirkulerte tekstiler etter å ha gått gjennom mekanisk resirkulering som er vist for andre typer materialer. Denne studien analyserte tekstiler fra to punkter i den sirkulære forsyningskjeden: avviste post-forbruker tekstiler samlet fra Fretex (n=30) og nyinnkjøpte tekstiler laget helt eller delvis av resirkulerte materialer (n=37) via målrettet PFAS-analyse ved bruk av ultra ytelse væske kromatografi kombinert med elektronsprayionisering og trippel kvadrupol massespektrometri. Det ble gjennomført en metodetest av to forskjellige protokoller for ekstraksjon av PFAS i faste prøver. Protokollen som brukte metanol som ekstraksjonsmiddel viste bedre ytelseegenskaper med henhold til gjenoppretting og matriseeffekter, og ble brukt som prøveopparbeidelse til tekstilprøvene. Alle tekstilprøvene ble vasket med vann før ekstraksjonen tok plass, og 10 av disse vannprøvene ble også analysert via målrettet PFAS-analyse. 96% av tekstilprøvene hadde minst én PFAS-påvisning, og PFOS hadde høyest deteksjonsfrekvens blant alle prøvene. Konsentrasjoner av total PFAS for alle prøvene varierte fra 0.05 - 98.29 ng/g og 0.001 - 3.338 ng/cm². Median verdier av total PFAS for post-forbruker tekstiler (16.82 ng/g, 0.379 ng/cm²) var høyere enn for resirkulerte tekstiler (3.32 ng/g, 0.181 ng/cm²). Kortkjededede PFCAer bidro mest til sammensetningen av PFAS i resirkulerte tekstiler, mens langkjededede PFSAer bidro mest til sammensetningen av post-forbruker tekstiler. Syntetiske materialer inneholdt vesentlig høyere konsentrasjoner av kortkjededede PFCAer og "andre PFAS", men en generell trend for alle PFAS-grupper med henhold til materialtyper ble ikke observert. Alle vannprøvene hentet fra vaskingen av tekstilprøvene hadde påvisning av minst en PFAS, og diSAMPAP ble påvist i alle. 3 tekstilprøver overskred EU's regulatoriske grenser for PFOS, men ingen prøver overskred grensene for PFOA.

Acknowledgments

Many people have helped me along the way with the work resulting in this thesis and I owe a great thanks to them all.

To my main supervisor Hans Peter Arp, thank you for the enthusiasm and support when I expressed the idea of working with textiles. Your eagerness and dedication to making the world better through science really shine through, and your work of putting pieces together for me, a hopeful and curious student who wanted to try something that was not necessarily listed as a pre-planned master project is greatly appreciated. You connected me with Anna Lennquist in ChemSec, when I did not even know an organization could do such cool and meaningful work as pushing companies to use safer chemicals full-time. Thank you Anna for your input, especially in relation to policy and regulation, and what is really going on in this area with regard to hazardous chemicals, a space I've never really dabbled in before. The passion both of you share for saving the planet is truly inspiring.

A huge thanks also goes out to the people helping me with the analytical chemistry. Gabriela Castro Varela helped me tremendously to get me started and confident in the lab work during the fall semester. Developing the method for this new matrix that we had not worked with before was interesting and fun. I wish you all the best in your new academic role and I am sure you are thriving. Thank you to Junjie Zhang for the help in the lab and processing of samples during the spring semester, as well as for the valuable answers to many questions during data analysis. My second co-supervisor Alexandros Asimakopoulos provided me with valuable insights and clarifications about the final data and interpretations of QAQC, which was highly appreciated.

Thank you to Theresa Kjell, also from ChemSec, who contributed with very helpful advice in the initial phase of developing the study.

Thank you to Geir Arne Bals from Fretex Miljø AS who facilitated and organized for me to come and gather post-consumer samples from the textile sorting section at Heggstadmoen, without hesitation. These samples comprise almost half of the sample batch and will give important information on chemical content in post-consumer textiles.

Lastly, I would like to thank my friends and family for their continuous support and love throughout my studies. The deepest thanks go out to Tobias, for not only endless emotional support, but also for never giving up on fixing big and small problems in Excel and Latex for me with zero complaints. Thank you to my brother Jonas, my biggest role model, for proofreading and showing that hard work pays off. My father's expression of kindness and support throughout all my years of study cannot be thanked enough. My mother, who was taken away by the illness, had a deep love of nature and a drive for making the world a better place. If I can even do something to follow your legacy now or in the future, I am content. You will forever be my inspiration.

List of Tables

3.1	Quality control procedure	31
4.1	Average Relative Standard Deviation (RSD) values for Absolute recoveries, Relative recoveries, and Matrix effect factors (MEF) for all target compounds in the quality control for the two protocols tested for the extraction of textile samples	32
4.2	Average Relative Standard Deviation (RSD) values for Absolute recoveries, Relative recoveries, and Matrix effect factors (MEF) for all target compounds in the quality control for the water samples	33
4.3	Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantification (LOQ) in ng/mL for each targeted PFAS for the textile samples	35
4.4	Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantification (LOQ) in ng/mL for each targeted PFAS for the water samples	36
4.5	Detection frequency, median, average (Avg.), minimum (Min.) and maximum (Max.) concentrations of 39 target analytes in ng/g for all samples (n=67). Values below LOD is excluded	39
4.6	Detection frequency (DF), median (Med.), average (Avg.), minimum (Min.) and maximum (Max.) concentrations of 39 target analytes for a selection of samples (n=50). Samples of yarn/thread/filling are excluded due to the inability of quantifying the sample area in ng/cm ² , along with values below LOD.	40
4.7	Detection frequencies for recycled textiles (n=37) and post-consumer textiles (n=30), divided into four groups, PFCAs (long and short chain), PFASs (long and short chain) and other PFASs.	45
4.8	Median concentrations (ng/g) of grouped PFAS in three categories of materials. Natural materials; recycled (n=17), and post-consumer (n=9). Synthetic materials; recycled (n=16), and post-consumer (n=8). Mixed materials; recycled (n=4), and post-consumer (n=2). Post-consumer samples without labels or unreadable labels were excluded.	48
4.9	Detection frequency (DF), median (Med.), average (Avg.), minimum (Min.) and maximum (Max.) concentrations in ng/ml of 10 water samples (third wash). 4 of the samples are from the washing of recycled textiles, and 6 is from the washing of post-consumer textiles	49
4.10	Ratios calculated by dividing the concentrations in textile samples (ng/g) by the concentrations in corresponding washing water samples (ng/ml).	50
4.11	Concentrations in various textiles from previous studies and this study divided into two units: ng/cm ² and ng/g	52
A.1	Sample information of all samples, recycled and post-consumer (labelled REC and FX). Sample ID, type of item, if made for adults/children/babies, type of material, country of origin and Ecolabel information	i
B.1	Concentrations in ng/ml for 10 water samples analyzed after the third wash. Target PFAS without any detections are excluded.	ii

C.1	Quality control parameters for 41 target compounds for the two methods tested: Protocol 1 (P1) and Protocol 2 (P2). Absolute recoveries (AR), Relative recoveries (RR), Matrix effects (ME), and RSD values for each respective parameter	iii
C.2	Quality control parameters for 43 target compounds for the water samples. Absolute recoveries (AR), Relative recoveries (RR), Matrix effects (ME), and RSD values for each respective parameter	iv
D.1	Concentrations (ng/g) of the recycled samples (labeled REC) for 15 target PFAS. Concentrations below LOD are excluded	v
D.2	Concentrations (ng/g) of the post-consumer samples obtained from Fretex (labeled FX) for 15 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD are excluded	vi
D.3	Concentrations (ng/g) of the recycled samples (labeled REC) for 10 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD are excluded. This table also includes the occurrence of different PFAS in each sample, and the calculated total PFAS concentrations (ng/g)	vii
D.4	Concentrations (ng/g) of the post-consumer samples obtained from Fretex (labeled FX) for 10 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD is excluded. This table also includes the occurrence of different PFAS in each sample, and the calculated total PFAS concentrations (ng/g)	viii
D.5	Concentrations (ng/cm ²) of the purchased recycled samples (labeled REC) for 13 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD is excluded.	ix
D.6	Concentrations (ng/cm ²) of the post-consumer textiles obtained from Fretex (labeled FX) for 13 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD are excluded.	x
D.7	Concentrations (ng/cm ²) of the purchased recycled samples (labeled REC) for 10 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD are excluded. This table also includes the calculated total PFAS concentrations (ng/cm ²)	xi
D.8	Concentrations (ng/cm ²) of the post-consumer samples obtained from Fretex (labeled FX) for 15 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD are excluded. This table also includes the calculated total PFAS concentrations (ng/cm ²)	xii

List of Figures

2.1	Molecular structure of PFAS with chain length of 8. Made using ChemDraw 19.1	4
2.2	Lifecycle stages of clothing that determine the rate of acquisition, retention, and release of chemicals and particles	11
2.3	Graphic representation of the circular economy model	16
3.1	The reject pile of post-consumer textiles at Fretex Heggstadmyra	26
3.2	Stages of sample pretreatment	28
3.3	Sample pool	28
3.4	Extracts from the pool sample using protocol 2 (after addition of 2 mL water) . .	29
3.5	SPE system	30
4.1	Box and whisker plot presenting total PFAS concentrations of all samples (n=67) in ng/g divided into two series, textile samples made with recycled materials (n=37) and post-consumer textiles (n=30)	42
4.2	Box and whisker plot presenting total concentrations of selected samples (n=37) in ng/cm ² divided into two series, textile samples made with recycled materials (n=20) and post consumer textiles (n=30). The total concentrations was calculated by addition of the concentrations of each target PFAS in each sample. . . .	43
4.3	Composition of different groups of PFAS for all recycled textiles (n=37) and post-consumer textiles (n=30) based on the detected PFAS concentration (ng/g) . . .	45
4.4	Median concentrations of grouped PFAS for three different material types; natural materials (n=26) synthetic materials (n=24) and mixed materials (n=6). Post-consumer samples without labels or unreadable labels were excluded.	47

List of Abbreviations

10:2 FTS 10:2 Fluorotelomer sulfonic acid

4:2 FTS 4:2 Fluorotelomer sulfonic acid

6:2 FTS 6:2 Fluorotelomer sulfonic acid

7H-PFHpA 7H-Dodecafluoroheptanoic acid

8:2 FTS 8:2 Fluorotelomer sulfonic acid

9Cl-PF3ONS 9-Chlorohexadecafluoro-3-oxanonane-1-sulfonate

AFIRM RSL The Apparel and Footwear International Restricted Substances List Management Group Restricted Substances List

APEO Alkylphenol ethoxylates

BPA Bisphenol A

CEAP EU's Circular Economy Action Plan

CLP Regulation on the Classification, Labelling, and Packaging of hazardous substances

Deca S Sodium-1-decanesulfonate

DEHP Diethylhexyl phtalate

diSAMPAP bis[2-(N-ethylperfluorooctane-1-sulfonamido)ethyl] phosphate

DMF Dimethylformamide

DWR Durable water repellent

ECHA The European Chemicals Agency

ESI Electrospray Ionization

EtFOSA Ethyl perfluorooctanesulfonamide

EtFOSAA N-methylPerfluoro-1-octanesulfonamide

EtFOSE Sulfluramid

EU European Union

FASAs Perfluoroalkane sulfonamide

FASEs Perfluoroalkyl sulfonamido ethanols

FOSAA Perfluoro-1-octanesulfonamidoacetic acid

FTOHs Fluorotelomer alcohols

Gen X 2,3,3,3-Tetrafluoro-2-(heptafluoropropoxy)propanoic acid

HPLC High Performance Liquid Chromatography

IS Internal Standard

LOD Limit of detection

LOQ Limit of quantification

LSE Liquid-solid extraction

MeFOSA Methyl perfluorooctanesulfonamide

MeFOSAA 2-(N-methylPerfluoro-1-octanesulfonamido)acetic acid

MeFOSE Methyl perfluorooctanesulfonyl fluoride

MeOH Methanol

mN/m milliNewton per meter

MOHs Mineral oil hydrocarbons

MS/MS Tandem Mass Spectrometry

N₂ Nitrogen Gas

NaDONA dodecafluoro-3H-4,8-dioxanonanoate

P37DMOA Perfluoro-3,7-dimethyloctanoic acid

PASF Perfluoroalkane sulfonyl fluoride

PFAAs Perfluoroalkyl acids

PFAS Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

PFBA Perfluorobutanoic acid

PFBS Perfluorobutanoic acid sulfonate

PFCAs Perfluoro carboxylic acids

PFDA Perfluorodecanoic acid

PFDoDA Perfluorododecanoic acid

List of Abbreviations

PFDoDS Perfluorododecane sulfonic acid
PFDS Perfluorodecane sulfonic acid
PFECHS Perfluoroethylcyclohexanesulfonic acid
PFHpA Perfluoroheptanoic acid
PFHpS Perfluoro-1-heptanesulfonate
PFHxA Perfluorohexanoic acid
PFHxDA Perfluoro-n-hexadecanoic acid
PFHxS Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid
PFNA Perfluorononanoic acid
PFNS Perfluorononane sulfonic acid
PFOA Perfluorooctanoic acid
PFOcDA Perfluorooctadecanoic acid
PFOS Perfluorooctano sulfonic acid
PFOSA Perfluorooctanesulfonamide
PFPeA Perfluoropentanoic acid
PFPeS Perfluoropentane sulfonic acid
PFSAs Perfluoroalkane sulfonic acids
PFTDA Perfluorotetradecanoic acid
PFTriDA Perfluorotridecanoic acid
PFUnA Perfluorodecanoic acid
POPs Persistent Organic Pollutants

List of Abbreviations

PP Polypropylene
PTFE Polytetrafluoroeten
PVC Polyvinyl chloride
QqQ Triple Quadruple Mass Spectrometry
REACH Regulation on Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals
SaMPAP 2-(N-ethylperfluorooctane-1-sulfonamido)ethyl phosphate
SPE Solid-phase extraction
SRMs Standard reference materials
SSCT EU's Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles
TA Target analyte
TOP Total oxidizable precursor
TULAC Textiles, upholstery, leather, apparel, and carpets
UAE Ultrasound assisted Extraction
UHPLC Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography
UN United Nations

Contents

List of Tables

List of Figures

List of Abbreviations

1	Introduction	1
2	Theory	3
2.1	PFAS	3
2.1.1	Definition and naming conventions of PFAS	3
2.1.2	Chemical properties	4
2.1.3	Toxicological properties	5
2.2	The Textile industry	6
2.2.1	Fibres and textiles	6
2.2.2	Use of PFAS in textiles	6
2.2.3	Occurrence of PFAS in functional textiles	7
2.2.4	Investigation of PFAS in non-functional textiles	8
2.2.5	Emission	9
2.2.6	Exposure	11
2.3	Policy	13
2.3.1	The Stockholm Convention	13
2.3.2	REACH and CLP	13
2.3.3	EU's Green Deal	14
2.3.4	Shift in industry	15
2.4	Transition to a more circular textiles economy	16
2.4.1	Principles of a circular economy	16
2.4.2	Textile recycling	16
2.4.3	Chemical Barriers for a Circular Economy	17
2.5	Analysis of PFAS in solid samples	19
2.5.1	Sample preparation	19
2.5.2	Liquid-Solid Extraction	19
2.5.3	Solid-Phase Extraction	19
2.6	Instrumentation	21
2.6.1	Liquid Chromatography	21
2.6.2	Electrospray Ionization	21
2.6.3	Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometry	21
2.7	Quality Assurance and Quality Control	23
2.7.1	Limit of Detection and Quantification	23
2.7.2	Internal Standard	23
2.7.3	Recovery	24

2.7.4	Matrix Effects	24
2.7.5	Quantification	25
3	Method	26
3.1	Sample collection	26
3.2	Chemicals and materials	26
3.3	Preparation of standard solutions	27
3.4	Sample pretreatment	27
3.5	Sample preparation	28
3.5.1	Sample extraction for protocol 1	29
3.5.2	Sample extraction for protocol 2	29
3.5.3	Sample extraction for water samples	30
3.5.4	Extraction of Textile Samples	30
3.6	Quality Assurance and Quality Control	31
3.7	UPLC-ESI-QqQ Analysis	31
3.8	Data Analysis	31
4	Results and discussion	32
4.1	Method performance	32
4.1.1	Recoveries	32
4.1.2	Matrix effects	34
4.1.3	LOD and LOQ	35
4.2	Occurrence of target PFAS in textiles	38
4.2.1	Comparison of recycled and post-consumer textiles	42
4.2.2	Distribution of different groups of PFAS in textiles	45
4.2.3	Comparison of different material types	47
4.3	Occurrence of target compounds in washing water	49
4.4	Comparison with literature	51
4.5	Comparison with regulatory limits	55
5	Implications, recommendations, and conclusions	56
5.1	Implications and recommendations for a cleaner circular economy	56
5.2	Final conclusions	57
A	Sample information	i
B	Concentrations in water samples	ii
C	Quality control parameters	iii
D	Concentrations in textile samples	v

1 Introduction

Focus and worries around Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) have increased over the last decades. PFAS are man-made substances and has been a major component in wet processing of functional textiles to achieve water-, oil-, and stain-repellence^[1]. It is well known that they are persistent in the environment, deserving of their name as “forever chemicals” and categorized as mobile and bioaccumulative, and some compounds have been shown to have toxicological properties^[2]. Due to their extreme persistence and mobility, they are prone to long-range transport and have been detected in the environment and biota from not only areas surrounding hotspots of PFAS emissions but also remote and pristine locations^[3] raising concerns of public and ecological health.

The main concern for the unmanageable spread of PFAS is due to their characterisation as very persistent^[4]. Once present in the environment, the removal is extremely difficult and the increase of concentration in the environment is a global environmental problem, but arguably often overruled by the earth’s heating temperature and could be referred to as an invisible climate crisis and not receiving its deserved attention at the same level. In the same fashion as global warming, the spread of very persistent substances is due to the major production of these chemicals for use in products that are in some cases non-essential for desired product characteristics^[5]. With a few exceptions, non-fluorinated alternatives are available for most products, but hard restrictions need to be in place for a phase-out of these chemicals in the industry to happen. NGOs like ChemSec and Greenpeace have been major drivers to influence big companies to substitute their use of PFAS to more eco-friendly alternatives as a response to the still increasing evidence base from the scientific community of their ubiquitous presence in the environment^[6]. It is even suggested that we have already overstepped the planetary boundaries when it comes to PFAS chemicals^[7].

The European Union have presented a set of policy initiatives through the European Commission to make the region climate neutral by 2050, under the overarching strategy of the European Green Deal. Along with this strategy the EU has proposed several ongoing policy initiatives like the Circular Economy Action Plan and the Zero Pollution Action Plan where the textile industry will have to make great adjustments to meet the set goals. More specifically, to adapt to The EU strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles along with the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability towards a Toxic Free environment and the Circular Economy Action Plan, the textile industry needs to increase the rate of textiles made of recycled materials and simultaneously substitute the most harmful chemicals and phase out the use of PFAS unless their use is essential. Growing the evidence base for what chemicals exists in the textiles that may be subject to recycling is an important part of achieving this goal. Currently, less than 1% of clothing is recycled into new clothing^[8], and mechanical recycling is the only technology currently operating on a large scale^[9]. This technology is unable to remove hazardous chemicals that may be present in the clothes that are being subject to recycling. Levels of persistent chemicals have been shown to accumulate in the recycling processes of other materials, and the risk is there for textiles as well^[9]. The aim to increase recycling rates of textiles whilst also achieving non-toxic

material cycles raises a question of trade-off and is a “chemical roadblock” for a circular textiles economy^{[10][9]}. A restriction on the manufacture and use of over 10 000 PFAS has recently been proposed by ECHA under REACH, supporting the ambitions under the EU’s Green Deal. The motivation of this proposal is the poor reversibility of PFAS already emitted to the environment, and they argue that the most efficient solution to combat the problem is zero use^[4]. This proposal is currently under evaluation and this thesis will contribute to the evidence base of PFAS presence in non-functional textiles in light of a circular economy and argue that this proposal should come to fruition.

The main aim of this thesis was to better understand how PFAS may be recirculated in the circular economy, by comparing PFAS concentrations in recycled textiles with post-consumer textiles sorted for reuse. Also, different groups of PFAS were analyzed to investigate the shift in the industry to shorter-chained analogs which is shown in functional textiles, as well as comparisons of different types of textile materials (natural, synthetic, and mixed) to see if some types of materials generally contain more PFAS than the others. Additionally, samples of water used to wash the textile samples was analyzed for PFAS to see if transfer to water from the washing of non-functional textiles occurs.

The scope of this thesis focuses on two points of the circular supply chain: rejected textiles collected from Norway’s biggest textile collector that was doomed for export (landfill/incineration) but have the potential of being sent back into the recycling loop if recycling technologies are better utilized in the future for new processing and manufacturing, and new textiles in the “use-phase” that is labeled as being made fully or partly from recycled textiles. A total of 67 items made of recycled textiles and post-consumer textiles was analyzed for 47 different targeted PFAS to get an overview of general concentration values that go in and out of our houses through the textile we wear, and have the opportunity to leak through the whole value chain, from production to use and waste.

The chosen textiles used as samples were not “functional textiles”, i.e. labeled as water- or oil-repellent, so PFAS in these products will not have been intentionally added, but a result of cross-contamination through the supply chain, including as processing aids during manufacturing and/or recycling. The levels of targeted PFAS in the samples will be measured by Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography coupled with Electrospray Ionisation and Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometry (UHPLC-ESI-QqQ-MS/MS).

2 Theory

2.1 PFAS

2.1.1 Definition and naming conventions of PFAS

PFAS are a large group of highly fluorinated aliphatic compounds containing the moiety C_nF_{2n+1} ^[11]. They are man-made chemicals, and estimates of the number of PFAS in the market or in patents have ranged from 4,700 to over 6 million^[12]. The acronym PFAS encompasses **per-** and **poly**fluorinated substances. For **perfluoroalkyl** substances *all* of the H- atoms in the C-H bonds in the non-fluorinated substance they are derived from have been replaced by F atoms, except those being substituted by a functional group. The structure can be written as $C_nF_{2n+1}-R$ ^[13], where R is the functional group attached at the end; commonly carboxylates or sulfonates. **Poly**fluorinated substances distinguish from **perfluoroalkyl** substances by not being fully fluorinated. All H atom attached to at least one (but not all) C atoms have been replaced by F atoms in such a manner that some polyfluorinated compounds could contain “scattered” or “grouped” multiple F atoms but they only belong to the PFAS family if it contains said moiety^{[13][11]}. They also have the potential to be transformed into perfluoroalkyl substances, either abiotically or biotically^[11].

The PFAS family can be divided into two primary classes: polymer and non-polymer. Polymers are large molecules formed by combining many identical smaller molecules (monomers) in a repeating pattern^[13]. For PFAS the polymer class includes the subclasses fluoropolymers, polymeric perfluoropolyethers (PFPE), and side-chain fluorinated polymers. Some of these are believed to cause less immediate toxicological risk for humans and ecosystems relative to some polymer PFAS and are not of the highest interest and priority at environmental release sites^[13].

The nonpolymer PFAS class encompasses the two major subclasses mentioned two paragraphs above: perfluoroalkyl substances and polyfluoroalkyl substances. The non-polymer PFAS class consists of 7 groups, one of them being perfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAs) the most commonly tested for PFAS group in the environment. PFAAs are sometimes referred to as “terminal PFAS” because degradation of many precursor polyfluoroalkyl substances may result in the formation of PFAAs, and no further degradation products will form from PFAAs under normal environmental conditions. Furthermore, PFAAs are divided into two major subgroups:

- Perfluorocarboxylic acids (PFCAs). Terminal degradation products of select precursors such as fluorotelomer alcohols (FTOHs).
- Perfluoroalkane sulfonic acids (PFSAs). Terminal degradation products of select precursors such as perfluoroalkyl sulfonamido ethanols (Perfluoroalkyl sulfonamido ethanols (FASEs)).

These two subgroups can further be divided into long-chain and short-chain depending on their carbon chain length. Short-chain PFCAs have 7 or less C-atoms, and long chain PFCAs have 8 or more. Short chain PFSAs have 5 or less C-atoms, whilst long-chain PFSAs have 6 or more^[13]. The distinction in chain length is made because those with similar lengths may behave similarly

Figure 2.1: Molecular structure of PFAS with chain length of 8. Made using ChemDraw 19.1

in terms of bioaccumulation and environmental fate^{[13][14]}. In this study the compounds are grouped into perfluorocarboxylic acids (PFCAs) perfluoroalkyl sulfonates (PFSA) while the rest are considered “other PFASs”. The PFCAs and PFSA are further divided into short- and longchain. These subgroups includes two of the most investigated PFAS over the past 15 years: PFOA (C = 8) a long chain PFCA, and PFOS (C = 8) a long-chain PFSA.^[13] PFAAs are typically the majority of target analyte PFAS included in commercial laboratories and are the primary focus of federal or state health-based guidance^[13].

2.1.2 Chemical properties

PFAS have unique physical and chemical properties that make them highly useful in a wide range of industrial applications.^[15] These properties stem from the fact that fluorine, the only element capable of replacing hydrogen in any organic molecule, has the highest electronegativity of all elements^[16]. Fluorine’s strong electronegativity towards its valence electrons makes carbon-fluorine (C-F) bonds exceptionally strong, highly polar, and relatively small^[16]. The steric repulsion of the fluorine substituents bound to carbon in the relative 1,3 positions shapes fluorocarbons in a rigid heliac structure^[15]. The stability of the C-F bond increases with the number of fluorine substituents bound to the same carbon atom, and the kinetic stability is derived from the steric shielding of the central atom by a “coating” of fluorine substituents^[15]. Therefore the stability of PFAS will vary depending on their chain length and degree of fluorination in addition to their functional groups^[14]. Fluorinated surfactants are stable to heat, acids, and bases, as well as reducing and oxidizing agents in organic systems^[17].

Fluorinated surfactants are highly efficient at reducing surface tension of its medium by selective adsorption on the interface, even at low concentrations^[17]. Fluorinated surfactants have been the first choice for a wide variety of different uses in industrial and commercial applications, due to their exceptional efficiency compared to other surfactants^{[17][14]}. They have been commercially available since the 1950s in applications like firefighting foams, waxes, paints, coatings, paper and most notably for this thesis, textiles^[6]. The interaction energy of water molecules with themselves is much greater than with fluorocarbon molecules, resulting in immiscibility between the two mediums^[16]. The fluorinated part of a PFAS molecule is hydrophobic and can lower the surface tension of a liquid, the interfacial tension between two liquids, or between a liquid and a solid^[11], hence exhibiting water, oil, and fat repellency when adsorbed on a substrate such as textiles^[17]. A concentration as low as 10 ppm of a fluorinated surfactant may lower the surface tension of water to 40 mN/m.

However, PFAS extreme chemical stability also means that they do not readily break down in the environment and have a significant impact on global ecosystems^{[15][6]}. The majority of PFAS are classified as very persistent and have gained the name “forever chemicals” in media due to their resistance to degradation. PFAS can be prone to long-range transport through both air and water, resulting in their widespread presence in the environment and biota^[6], including even remote areas such as the Arctic^{[3][18]}. This was not predicted when the substances were first introduced into industrial mass production and insufficient knowledge and tools to handle the problem resulted in the ubiquitous presence^[15]. This has led to growing concerns about the environmental impact of PFAS and a need for better understanding and management of these substances.

2.1.3 Toxicological properties

Some widely used PFAS have become the focus of environmental concern due to their extreme persistence and evidence of negative physiological effects^[15]. While “regular” aliphatic fluorocarbons are generally unreactive and essentially “ignored” by organisms, some fluorine-containing substances can be highly toxic^[15]. PFAS have a high affinity for protein binding and tend to accumulate in organs like kidney, liver, spleen and brain of various organisms^[19]. During pregnancy, these chemicals can cross the placental barriers and reach the fetus. Additionally, transfer through breastfeeding is well documented which is a major concern since babies and children may be more sensitive to the negative effects of chemicals such as PFAS^[2]. In laboratory studies, the adverse effects of PFAAs varies widely based on chain length. The serum elimination half-lives of PFAAs can vary greatly, from hours to years, with longer-chained PFAAs being much more persistent in the body, than the short-lengths^[2]. Even though the short-chained PFAS (e.g. PFBS, PFBA and PFHxA) are assumed to have a lower bioaccumulation potential they have high mobility in soil and water and are extremely persistent in the environment, making it impossible to reverse exposure, which is regarded as a hazard in itself. Long-term toxicological effects may occur in the future, when certain effect thresholds are reached^[20]. Health effects caused by PFAS include hepatic effects, immunological effects, endocrine disrupting effects, cardiovascular effects, endocrine effects, reproductive effects, developmental effects, high cholesterol and cancer^{[19][2][21]}. While most toxicological studies have looked at PFAAs, evidence for the majority of emerging PFAS is scarce^[19].

Some fluoroorganic compounds can be degraded to toxic metabolites when ingested, including fluoro-fatty acids, aldehydes, alcohols, amines, and related compounds^[15]. Perfluoroisobutene, the most toxic fluorinated compound discovered to date, has an LC₅₀ of less than 1 ppm, targets the liver and lungs^[15]. This compound, along with other (less toxic) perfluoro olefins, can be formed at elevated temperatures during the pyrolysis of the fluorinated polymer polytetrafluoreten (PTFE), which is widely used as an anti-stick coating for household appliances^[15] and textiles^[22] where the the most familiar uses are in Teflon^[22] and Gore-Tex^[23]. Inhalation of steam from heating PTFE over 200°C could lead to “polymer fume fever”, although this condition is rare and usually only occurs in smokers when tobacco or cigarette paper is contaminated by PTFE-containing plastic dust^[24]. Some major producers have started to replace these surfactants with more readily degradable alternative compounds, but not nearly all^[15].

2.2 The Textile industry

2.2.1 Fibres and textiles

The term *textile* was initially defined as woven fabric^[25], but it now includes any material made of interlacing fibers, filaments, or yarns, both natural and synthetic^[25]. A fiber is a thin thread of a natural or artificial substance^[26]. Depending on their properties, these materials can serve different functions. Woven and knitted fabrics are used to make clothing and home textiles, while non-woven textiles are used in products like insulation and geotextiles. Textiles are typically made from polymers which can be plastic-based (e.g polyester, nylon, acrylic and elastane), cellulose-based (e.g cotton, viscose, lyocell, linen, hemp, and jute) or protein-based (e.g. wool and silk)^[8]. In 2020 the global fiber consumption was dominated by synthetic fibers (65,4%), whilst cellulosic and protein-based fibers made up the remainder (34.6%). It is estimated that by 2030, global fiber production will reach approximately 140 million tons, with synthetic fiber accounting for the majority of that production (108 million tons)^[26]. The term *apparel* can be used to refer to personal outfits, clothing, and attire^[25].

2.2.2 Use of PFAS in textiles

It is estimated that over 8,000 different chemicals are used to turn raw materials into textiles and 43 million tonnes of chemicals are used annually to produce textiles^[8]. A significant number of chemicals have not been evaluated for their impacts, so their risks are unknown. Chemicals are used at several stages: from fiber production, to dyeing, treating, and finishing processes, often to give specific properties to the items. The primary functions for the use of PFAS in textiles are water, oil, and dirt repellence due to their surfactant-like properties as explained in section 2.1.2. Other functionality like thermal resistance, breathability and moisture-wicking are advantages of using PFAS technology in textiles^{[27][28]}. PFAS, particularly sidechain fluorinated polymers, have been used in the textile industry as surface protectors for products such as apparel, leather, carpets, and paper. These uses have led to widespread consumer contact with PFAS-containing products. Substances used at all stages of the production process often remain in textiles, both intentionally and unintentionally^[8].

The stage where PFAS are intentionally added to textiles is in *textile finishing*, which refers to the treatment of a base fabric by a mechanical or chemical finishing process to enhance the appearance, aesthetics, properties, and performance to meet the functional requirements in the final product^[25]. The base fibers could be either natural, manufactured, or a fiber blend^[25]. Oil- and water-repellent properties are important on textile products designed for uses such as outdoor wear, military clothing, some workwear and accessories like umbrellas. The term waterproof applies to textile materials able to prevent the absorption of water and the penetration of water into the textile-structure. Most technical fabrics used in apparel benefit from the transpiration of air and moisture through the fabric to maintain thermophysical and thermophysiological comfort for the wearer which can be achieved by applying water-repellent finishes to porous textile fabrics^[25]. Water- and oil-repellence has historically been achieved with textile finishes that contain fluoropolymers or a polymer to which perfluoroalkyl groups

have been attached. These fluorinated polymers often contain residual raw materials and trace levels of perfluoroalkyl acids (PFAAs) as impurities^[29]. The use of PFAS is as of now the best available technology for achieving the combination of all these characteristics. However, several non-fluorinated fabric repellants have been shown to provide similar rates of water repellency to PFAS-finished fabrics and it is argued that the use of PFAS chemistry for garments where oil repellency is in excess of user requirements is over-engineering^[5]. Chemical finishing processes is the production step with the most significant pollution potential^[30].

Other uses of PFAS in textile production include use as wetting agents to enhance dyeing and as penetration aids for bleaches. PFOA-related compounds have been used as antifoaming agents in the dyeing process^[1]. Manufacturing equipment and machinery often use lubrication for smooth running, or they are sprayed with chemicals to hinder things to stick to them. These lubrication oils and sprays could contain PFAS^[1] and trace amounts can transfer from the machine onto the fabric^[28]. Some cleaning products used by both consumers and manufacturing plants use fluorinated ingredients as antifoaming agents^{[1][28]}, which also could cause trace amounts on fabrics if they are not rinsed properly^[28]. Recycled synthetic fibers could also retain chemicals from the plastic products it was derived from, like how it has been suggested that the use of PFAS in the production of plastic may explain why PFAS are found in artificial turf. PFAS have been used as mould release agents, foam blowing agents, foam regulators, polymer processing aids, in the etching of, and as curatives in the production of plastic^[1].

2.2.3 Occurrence of PFAS in functional textiles

The European Commission published a report in 2020 assessing the use of PFAS and non-fluorinated alternatives in textiles, upholstery, leather, apparel, and carpets (TULAC). The report revealed that PFAS are predominately used in these applications as opposed to non-fluorinated alternatives. Groups of PFAS used and are in use for TULAC applications includes fluoropolymers, side-chain fluorinated polymers, and non-polymeric PFAS (PFCAs, PFSAs, perfluoroalkane sulfonyl fluoride (Perfluoroalkane sulfonyl fluoride (PASF))-derivatives and fluorotelomers). It is in some cases difficult to state if specific substances were used intentionally, is an impurity or the product of degradation, and the presence of potential impurities or unreacted monomers within polymer compounds remained unclear. However, it is known that PFCAs, PFSAs, and fluorotelomers have been/are used intentionally, while it is believed that (PASF)-based derivatives are impurities since they are used as production aids in fluoropolymer synthesis. The report also identified that oil-repellence was essential for high-performance textiles like certain types of personal protective wear (PPE) and textiles used in medical applications^[27]. Other investigations have confirmed the widespread use of PFAS in various types of apparel, including treated apparel (mostly for outdoor use or sports), military clothing, workwear for medical staff, and firefighting gear. Groups of detected PFAS include PFCAs, PFSAs, FASAs, , fluorotelomer olefins, fluorotelomer alcohols (FTOHs)^[31], side-chain fluorinated polymers with PFBS-related side chains (polymer), side-chain fluorinated acrylate polymers and PTFE^[1]. Estimations of consumption of PFAS in TULAC products range from 45 000 to 142 000 tonnes per year as of 2020^{[27][4]}, with home textiles (50-53%) and consumer apparel (34-39%) being the dominant sectors^[27].

Globally, not all manufacturers of apparel are required to disclose what chemicals they use in their production, and what is being released from their sites. The EU has a policy that manufacturers need to list their use, and it needs to be in compliance with restrictions. The majority of textile production happens outside of the EU, and extended use of hazardous chemicals could be kept as corporate secrets. Discoveries made by environmental organizations and scientists using modern analytical techniques could expose these companies.

Greenpeace recently conducted an investigation where they purchased and screened 47 items from the ultra-fast fashion brand SHEIN for hazardous chemicals^[32]. The analysis revealed levels of hazardous chemicals present in 15% of the products exceeding the EU's environmental regulations. All of these products were made fully or partly from synthetic, fossil-fuel-based materials and most of them were boots or shoes. 32% of the products contained hazardous chemicals at levels of concern, including DMFs and lead. At least one hazardous chemical was quantified in 45 of the 47 products, although most were at relatively lower levels. These products are being widely sold in Europe, potentially impacting consumers. Greenpeace further suggested that SHEIN has little oversight of hazardous chemical management within its supply chain, which could potentially harm workers and impact the environment and local communities. Only 8 samples of swimwear were analyzed for PFAS and no detection occurred. However, the reported detection limits ranged from 5 to 21 ng/g^[32], higher than the best modern analytical techniques can report. The PFAS levels in the rest of the samples that were not subject to PFAS analysis is unknown.

A separate investigation in Canada analyzed 38 samples of children's, adult's and maternity clothes and accessories bought from three online retailers, SHEIN, Zaful and AliExpress. One in five items had elevated levels of hazardous chemicals, including lead, PFAS and phthalates. A SHEIN jacket for toddlers contained 20 times the amount of lead than the safe level set by Health Canada. Experts commenting on the finding described the presence of hazardous chemicals as "hazardous waste". For instance, a pink raincoat purchased from AliExpress contained 220.5 ng/g PFAS, considered high by experts^[33].

2.2.4 Investigation of PFAS in non-functional textiles

Chemical additives and their concentrations in most product labels are rarely listed, making it challenging for consumers to assess the level of hazardous chemicals in the products. Studies using analytical techniques can estimate concentrations of chemicals in apparel. Most studies investigating PFAS levels in textiles have considered functional^{[34][35][36][37]} or domestic textiles^{[38][39]} marked as stain/water repellent where the content of PFAS was expected to be high. Some studies have also analyzed the effect of weathering of PFAS from durable water-repellent (DWR) clothing^{[40][41]}. There have been a few studies investigating PFAS levels in materials where no impregnation is expected to have occurred. Many of these have focused on products for children and infants since they are at higher risk when exposed to toxic chemicals^{[42][34][43][37][44][45]}.

In a recent study, a wide range of products, including furnishing, apparel, and bedding for children and adolescents, were evaluated to assess if the product labels could be an indicator for

consumers to choose PFAS-free products. The products were divided into groups on whether they were labeled as being water- and or stain-resistant and “green” assurances. The study used total fluorine screening, targeted PFAS analysis, and analysis of PFAAs through total oxidizable precursor (TOP) assay. They showed that products marketed as water- and/or stain-resistant had more frequent detections and higher concentrations of total fluorine than those without such claims. 4/14 products that were not labeled with water or stain resistance had detections for the total fluorine analysis with a concentration over the LOD of 10 ppm. None of these products had detections in the targeted PFAS analysis. PFAAs generated by precursor oxidation using the TOP assay often exceeded pre-oxidation concentrations from targeted PFAS analysis. Results also suggested that green assurances do not indicate the absence of PFAS, and that there are many non-essential uses of PFAS in products used by children^[46]. The presence of PFAS in female period underwear and active wear has been revealed where the levels found were considered high enough to suggest that PFAS were intentionally added during manufacturing^{[47][48]}, even if they are not DWR items. Some of the products with detected high levels of fluorine had the OEKO-TEX[®] certification confirming “green” assurances do not guarantee the absence of PFAS. The eco-wellness cite conduction the investigation on active wear interviewed a Managing Director within the OEKO-TEX[®] standard in the United States who said that they only test for 30+ of the most common PFAS with targeted analysis, and not for total fluorine^[28].

H&M and IKEA initiated a large scale study in 2019 that looked at chemical content in mechanically shredded post-consumer cotton (> 90%), polyester (> 90%) and wool (> 80%) waste from various regions worldwide. 2.5% of the datapoints showed undesirable detections and less than 1% exceeded The Apparel and Footwear International Restricted Substances List Management Group Restricted Substances List (AFIRM RSL) limits^[49]. They found that post-consumer polyester samples had the widest variety of substances detected, and in post-consumer wool samples almost all samples contained at least one substance that failed against AFIRM RSL limits^{[50][49][51]}. PFAS was only detected in polyester samples and at minimal values and detection frequency^[51].

2.2.5 Emission

PFAS emissions to the environment can be directly attributed to manufacturing, use, and disposal or as impurities in emitted substances. Indirect sources of PFAS result from the transformation of precursor substances in the environment, wildlife, or humans, like biotransformation or atmospheric degradation, e.g. PFOA formed from the biotransformation of 8:2 FTOH^[11]. Chemicals used in textile production may be retained in finished products, affecting the wearer, and could be released into ecosystems during washing or when discarded after use^{[40][8]}. The dominant life-cycle stage for emissions is suggested to be the use-cycle phase for frequently washed textiles, followed by textile treatment, where processing of textiles with PFAS-species occur before sale^[27]. Estimated annual emissions of PFAS from the use phase related to new products on the market range from 10 000 to 35 000 tonnes per year. With the exception of applications of fluorinated gases, TULAC applications have the largest PFAS load to the environment, mostly caused by the high tonnages of PFAS used in the products^[4].

The textiles industry is a major user of hazardous chemicals, with 25% of chemicals produced worldwide are used in textiles^[8], resulting in heavy pollution of rivers, air, and agricultural land worldwide. PFOA and PFOS, along with many more toxic substances like Polyvinyl chloride (PVC), Phthalates, Alkylphenol ethoxylates (APEO), and heavy metals are found in textile products^[52]. Textile production discharges high volumes of water containing hazardous chemicals into the environment and 20% of industrial water pollution globally is attributable to the dyeing and treatment of textiles^[8]. Areas with a high density of textile production have experience color changes of rivers due to the dyeing and processing of clothes for global clothing brands. This has resulted in the destruction of local ecosystems, such as the Citarum River in Indonesia, thought of as the most polluted river in the world, with over 200 textile factories releasing dyes and other chemicals into the water along its banks^[53]. These colorful effluents give a visual representation of a sometimes invisible problem: hazardous chemicals released into the environment by industry^[54] that will impact the health and livelihoods of local communities specifically in the Global South^[54]. When Greenpeace sampled the effluent of two large textile suppliers in China, the largest textile manufacturing hub in the world, and screened them to see if textile factories in China were using and discharging them into waterways, they found a wide range of hazardous chemicals including alkylphenols which are banned for use in textile manufacturing in Europe as well as PFAS. The problem of emissions of hazardous chemicals is thus not solved by the modern wastewater treatment plants installed next to these factories and Greenpeace then argued for zero use as the only option and traced custody back to the global sportswear brands making their clothes at these facilities^[54].

Emissions of PFOA, PFNA and other by-products from production sites have been documented where the emissions lead to widespread contamination of air, soil, water, and food. But little is known about where PTFE and other fluorinated polymers are produced in the world as there is no regulations forcing producers of polymer PFAS to disclose the production location. No regulation has been pushed since polymer PFAS is believed to pose less immediate risk^[13]. Still, several harmful substances have been reported in wastewater or river water downstream of plants known to be manufacturing fluorinated polymers. Some well known instances are the widespread pollution from fluoropolymer facilities in the United States such as DuPont (now Chemours) and 3M manufacturing sites. PFOA, used as a dispersion agent, in PTFE was emitted to lakes, rivers, soil, and groundwater through wastewater treatment plants, landfills and emissions to the air^[55].

Landfills containing textile waste are another source of PFAS emissions, where substances used in the manufacturing of textiles that remain in the final product may leak hazardous substances^[56]. It is difficult for waste management to know exactly which substances are present in discarded products and to what concentration levels since information regarding chemical substances in textiles is often limited when going down the supply chain^[56]. Also, the vast majority of garbage including textiles ends up being incinerated where terminal PFAS could be formed. PTFE, marketed as safe to use could be burned and form the very toxic perfluoroisobutene (as explained in section 2.1.3), so even if PTFE-containing products are marketed as safe to use, they could pose a high threat during the products end of life stage^[22].

2.2.6 Exposure

The main PFAS exposure routes for humans and the environment is through contaminated water and food, PFAS-containing consumer products, household dust and air^[21]. Due to the widespread distribution, environmental degradation, and metabolism of the PFAS released into the environment, a very complex exposure situation exists. As a result, the relative contribution to human exposure from different routes or from a single source is not yet known^[57]. There is growing evidence that clothing is an important source of exposure to various chemicals and particles on a daily basis. Emerging knowledge suggests that everyday clothing harbors various contaminants, which if inhaled, ingested, or dermally absorbed, could carry significant health risks^[58].

People spend most of their lives in intimate contact with clothing, and will be exposed to the chemicals found on and in their clothing via inhalation, ingestion, and dermal absorption^[58]. Chemicals can be released from clothing and particles could enter people's mouths that can be absorbed in the body and contribute to negative health effects^[58] and ingestion by mouthing of fabrics can be a significant exposure pathway for young children. Some studies have revealed dermal absorption to be a significant contributor to the total human exposure to chemicals such as brominated flame retardants, through contact with furniture^[59] and house dust particles^[60]. In order for a chemical to be available for absorption through the skin it has to be dissolved in solution, i.e. dissolved into the body fluid (sweat/sebum/saliva), while in contact with the skin to become bioaccessible. A portion of that can then be absorbed and reach the systemic circulation and become bioavailable. Very few studies have included dermal uptake as a possible route for human exposure to PFAS, and little is known about the dermal absorption potential of different types of PFAS^[61].

Figure 2.2: Lifecycle stages of clothing that determine the rate of acquisition, retention, and release of chemicals and particles. Reprinted with permission from D. Licina, G.C. Morrison, G. Beko, C.J. Weschler and W.W. Nazaroff, Clothing-mediated exposures to chemicals and particles, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2019, 53, 5559–5575, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b00272>. Copyright (2023) American Chemical Society

The chemicals present in clothing are a mix of those present at the time of purchase and those acquired post-purchase. This mix changes with cleaning practices, storage, and wear^[58]. Some chemicals in clothing fabrics are present as a consequence of packaging, transport, storage, and

other processes that occur between manufacture and purchase. Laundering and dry-cleaning remove certain chemicals from clothing but can add others. When dried, the clothing can adsorb chemicals from the air in which it is dried. PFAS are found in home dust worldwide^[62], which could be caused by indoor-textiles, but is also a cause for chemicals to be reabsorbed in attire used in environments containing dust. Precursor chemicals on clothing can also be chemically transformed into other species. The rate of acquisition and release of chemicals through continuous use of a clothing item can therefore vary and is difficult to measure^[58].

Workers in the textile industry are chronically exposed to textile process dust from particularly wool and cotton, which could lead to occupational asthma and respiratory irritation^[63]. A study investigating PFAS in wastewater, air, airborne particles, and settled dust in a textile manufacturing plant in China, found that PFOA and PFDA or their precursor compounds 8:2 FTOH and 10:2 FTOH were the dominant compounds in all media tested. The workers' exposure to FTOHs via air inhalation was up to 5 orders of magnitude higher than the background exposure of the general western population^[64].

2.3 Policy

2.3.1 The Stockholm Convention

For a long time the prevailing mindset that toxic pollution could be diluted and dispersed in the environment was widely held by many in industry and governments. But years of campaigning by the environmental movement made legislators and companies begin to shift towards a more precautionary approach by restricting and banning hazardous chemicals. This resulted in the 1998 agreement of the Stockholm convention, banning the most well-known hazardous and persistent chemicals at the time^[54]. In May 2009 Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS), its salts and perfluorooctane sulfonyl fluoride (POSF) was amended to the list of POPs in the Stockholm Convention with acceptable purposes and specific exemptions^[65]. Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), its salts and PFOA-related compounds with specific exemptions was amended to the list in May 2019, followed by perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS), its salts, and PFHxS-related compounds without specific exemptions being amended in June 2022^[65]. The exclusions made for PFOS and PFOA did not include use in textiles for commercial products, so their restriction shifted the use in industry to other PFAS, often of shorter chain lengths^[21]. In many applications PFHxS has been used as a replacement for PFOS in textiles, leather and upholstery^[65].

2.3.2 REACH and CLP

The European Union has a comprehensive framework on chemical legislation towards the chemicals industry comprising approximately 40 legislative instruments including the Regulation on Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), agreed in 2006, and the Regulation on the Classification, Labelling and Packaging of hazardous substances (CLPs) and others that are aiming to protect human health and the environment from risks posed by chemicals and has an impact on most companies across the EU by placing a burden of proof on companies use of chemicals in manufacture and product they place on the market in the EU^[66]. The restrictions were supported by several global clothing brands. However, positive regulatory developments are slow to come into force, still contain loopholes, and are just starting to address the problem of numerous unregulated hazardous chemicals^[54]. A number of PFAS are on the REACH Candidate List of substances of very high concern, for example PFHxS, PFBS and PFHpA^[67].

Due to increased awareness of exposure to hazardous chemicals in textiles through skin contact/inhalation or unintentional ingestion of dust released from the materials, strict concentration limits are set under the persistent organic pollutants (POPs) Regulation (EC) 2019/1021 as a part of REACH for a range of hazardous substances for product sold in Europe (whether present as additives or contaminants). Set limits for PFAS only currently exist for PFOA (<25 ng/g), and PFOS (< 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2 = 0.1 \text{ ng}/\text{cm}^2$)^[68].

2.3.3 EU's Green Deal

In December 2019 the European Commission presented The European Green Deal describing a holistic approach to the EU's climate and environmental policy^{[69][70]}. The aim is to ensure a more sustainable and circular economic development with less pollution, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and better public health^[69]. The Green Deal is described as an important part of the European Commission's strategy to implement the UN's 2030 agenda and sustainability goals. It is desired that all actors in the industry should work together to combine better health and environmental protection to increase global competitiveness and the degree of transparency in the assessments of chemicals^[69].

A key commitment of the European Green Deal is EU's *Zero-Pollution Ambition* to reduce air, water and soil pollution to levels harmless to health and the environment with the goal to create a toxic-free environment by 2050. Actions involve reducing pollution from production and consumption, and implement and enforce pollution laws more strictly^[71]. The *Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability* is part of EU's Zero-Pollution Ambition. The strategy aims to better protect citizens and the environment and boost innovation for safe and sustainable chemicals. The strategy places PFAS policy front and centre^[67] by having a stand alone action point stating "Phasing out the use of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in the EU, unless their use is essential"^[72]. One more key message is that the same limit value for hazardous substances should apply to both virgin and recycled material. Another building block of the EU Green Deal is the *Circular Economy Action Plan* (CEAP) focusing on reducing pressure on natural resources within selected sectors that use the most resources and where the potential for circularity is high. The textile sector is highly prioritised in CEAP^[73]. In light of the complexity of the textile value chain the European Commission proposed a comprehensive EU strategy solely focusing on textiles-based industry; the *EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles* (SSCT). It implements the commitments of the EU Green Deal; the CEAP and Zero Pollution Ambition along with the Industrial Strategy. Being connected to the strategies mentioned above, the SSCT highlights the importance of tackling the presence of hazardous chemicals while at the same time encouraging industry to boost textile sorting, re-use, and recycling^[74]. Subsequently, the EU aims to move towards toxic-free material cycles and clean recycling^[75]. The Commission's 2030 Vision for Textiles lists: all textile products placed on the EU market are durable, repairable, recyclable, and to a great extent made of recycled fibers whilst being free of hazardous substances and produced respecting social rights^[76].

On the 7th of February 2023 ECHA published a restriction proposal under REACH of more than 10 000 PFAS, prepared by authorities in Norway, Germany, The Netherlands, Sweden, and Denmark. It supports the ambitions of The EU's Chemicals Strategy and the Zero Pollution Action Plan and addresses all uses of PFAS. The motivation is that if PFAS release is not minimized, threshold levels will be reached in the environment that will negatively affect people and ecological health. The main concern leading to the proposal is PFAS very high persistence in the environment and the extreme challenge of removing them once emitted leading to constantly increasing concentrations. If constant emissions continue the exposure of humans and the environment to these substances will inevitably lead to negative effects. ECHA's scientific

committees are currently evaluating the proposal^[4].

It is clear that the policy has complied with recommendations from research discovering the enormous use and unmanageable release of hazardous chemicals from the textile industry and increasing pressure from environmental activists in recent years. Still, the most comprehensive legislation and strategies only apply within the EU, yet this is a global problem where those with less are most affected. Voluntary action can only go so far, there will always be companies who will do nothing unless they are required to by regulation, and could cut corners on the use of hazardous chemicals and water pollution. Enforcing the regulations that do exist are important to avoid companies taking advantage of this too^[77].

2.3.4 Shift in industry

The gradual regulations of PFAS mainly targeted PFOA, PFOS, and PFHxS (long chained-PFAAs), due to evidence of their persistent, bioaccumulative, and toxic properties. Industries using these compounds needed alternatives for production, so most started using short-chain PFAS instead. Short-chain PFAS are assumed to have lower bioaccumulation potential, but they also have other properties of concern like high mobility in soil and water as well as extreme persistence. Long-term effects in organisms of short-chained PFAS that will stay in the environment once emitted are unknown and a huge cause for concern^[20]. Nevertheless, production continued with short-chained PFAS as alternatives and several studies have seen the shift in textiles with detection of more long-chained PFAS in functional textiles purchased before 2011/2012^[78]^[36], versus more detections of short-chained PFAS in products purchased after 2012^[40]^[43].

2.4 Transition to a more circular textiles economy

To achieve the ambitious goals under the umbrella strategy of the Green Deal, a key problem needs to be addressed: a circular economy cannot happen without designing out harmful substances as an absolute prerequisite.

2.4.1 Principles of a circular economy

A circular economy is a departure from the traditional linear economic model based on a take, make, use and dispose pattern. It reduces waste by extending the life cycle of products by sharing, leasing, reusing, repairing, refurbishing and recycling existing materials and products for as long as possible. Benefits include slowdown of the use of natural resources along with reduction in land use and total annual greenhouse gas emissions^[79].

Figure 2.3: Graphic representation of the circular economy model. By the European Parliament^[79]

Clothing represents more than 60% of total textiles used globally, and in the last 15 years, clothing production has approximately doubled^[8]. The current clothing system of producing, distributing, and using clothing operates in an almost completely linear way and puts pressure on resources, pollutes the environment and creates negative societal impact. Less than 1% of material that is used to produce clothing is recycled into new clothing. Across the industry, only 13% of the total material input is in some way recycled after clothing use, cascading to other industries and use in lower-value applications like insulation material, wiping cloths, and mattress stuffing, likely to constitute the final use. Much of the collected clothing is exported to countries with no collection infrastructure of their own, so most end up in landfills or are cascaded to lower-value applications. Today's linear system uses large amounts of resources and has negative impacts on the environment and people. The industry also uses non-renewable resources like oil to produce synthetic fibres, fertilisers to grow cotton, and chemicals to produce, dye and finish fibres and textiles^[8].

2.4.2 Textile recycling

No clothing-to-clothing recycling currently exists at scale. Most apparel products are not designed for disassembly, which is an important factor for recycling. Fabric blends cannot easily

be recycled by mechanical means. Most recycled textiles are downcycled into other products, such as wipes and insulation, rather than used to make new textiles for the apparel industry. Recycling reduces a product back to its basic material level before remaking those materials into new products^[8].

Mechanical or chemical methods can be used to create new textile materials. Most known methods are economically and technologically immature, and thus do not allow textiles to be recyclable in practice and at scale^[9]. In mechanical recycling, natural textiles such as cotton and wool are sorted by colour, and then cut and shredded into smaller pieces. Fibers are aligned and often mixed with virgin material to improve strength, if used for apparel. Some textile mills are integrating pre-consumer textiles into their fabric offering, especially in the denim industry. 100% synthetic fibers such as nylon or polyester, can also be mechanically recycled. The fabric is sorted by colour, washed, cut, shredded, melted, and extruded into new pellets. Most recycled polyester fibers used in apparel originate from plastic bottles and not from polyester fabrics or clothing, mainly because polyester in clothes is often blended with other materials^[9]. Toxic contaminants remain in mechanically recycled textiles, so use of this process faces the challenge of toxic contaminants from secondary materials that could potentially accumulate in recycled materials. Chemical recycling methods is the only technology that allows the removal of hazardous chemicals from garments but it is not well-developed for textile recycling.

Recycling cannot be seen as the ultimate solution for addressing chemicals in the system, there is a clear need to design out toxic chemicals upstream, eliminating the need for chemicals to enter the material system in the first place, or substituting safer alternatives where possible. Lack of methods to decontaminate recycled textiles is an important reason why designing out chemicals of concern is the most efficient way to tackle the problem^[9]. (flytt)

2.4.3 Chemical Barriers for a Circular Economy

The desire for an increase in the circulation of materials in CEAP and a reduction in the spread of hazardous substances in the Chemicals strategy and the Zero Pollution ambition raises a conflict and question of trade-off. These ambitions are also mentioned in the UN's Sustainable Development Goals, making this problem arise across industries and borders. It can be described as "The policy conflict between circularity and toxicity"^[10], and Chemsec labeled the problem of hazardous chemicals in recycled textiles the "missing piece" and a "chemical roadblock" for a circular economy^[9]. The core of the problem is that by retaining materials to achieve circularity, one may preserve hazardous substances in the economy. Unrestrained circulation of waste may increase the spread of hazardous substances, while hard-set limits on hazardous substances may reduce circulation.

The collected textile material put into the recycling systems today often has been placed on the market long before the present legal requirements on substances entered into force. Recycled textile materials may contain higher amounts of hazardous substances than virgin materials. A test performed by the Swedish Chemicals Agency in 2012 found much higher concentrations of phthalates in a second-hand t-shirt (only one second-hand t-shirt was tested in the study) than in

29 new shirts^[56]. Often different polymers and substances are mixed in the collection of waste, and product made from the same polymer can differ significantly in their chemical contents. The outcome of recycling processes creating secondary resources, are therefore generally more contaminated than the corresponding resources taken from the bedrock. This has shown to be a problem for plastics, metals and paper^{[9][10][80]} and is an issue that must be addressed if high increase of recycled textiles comes to fruition.

In a circular economy, the chemical content of a product depends not only on what is added during the production process, but also on what is already present in the material. As a consequence, continuous use of a chemical results in the accumulation of that chemical over the recycling cycles^{[81][80]}. Some are perpetuated through the production and processing of recycled materials, while others are linked to cross-contamination during recycling. Even after a rapid phase out of production and use, legacy hazardous chemicals may remain in material cycles for a long time, resulting in long-term exposure and potential human health impacts^[9]. A study of paper recycling, modelled the amounts of Bisphenol A (BPA), diethylhexyl phthalate (DEHP), and mineral hydrocarbons (MOHs) that accumulate over time in a recycling system. When it was assumed that constant amounts of the chemicals were added to new paper products, the levels continued to rise for 25 years for BPA, 31 years for MOHs and 45 years for DEHP, before reaching steady state. The results of the modelling indicated that phasing out of chemicals is the most effective way for reducing chemical contamination, opposed to decontamination. However, this required a considerable amount of time after the phase out period before the chemical content of the paper could be considered insignificant, 15 years for DEHP, 13 years for MOHs, and 31 years for BPA. Also the chemicals in the model were assumed to be intentionally added to the paper material, so chemical contamination during use was not considered^[80].

Increased use of virgin materials and low recycling levels show that a circular economy is far from realised. The presence of chemicals of concern in materials is a huge barrier for a circular economy. Mechanical recycling is unable to detoxify the secondary products, and will remain the main recycling technology for the foreseeable future, which makes establishing non-toxic waste-streams the key to scaling up the circular economy^[9]. The Ellen McArthur Foundation has proposed a vision for a “New Textiles Economy”^[8] where one out of four ambitions include phasing out substances of concern by aligning industry and creating safe material cycles, aligning with the goals of the European Green Deal. To improve transparency along the value chain, a robust evidence base of the content of chemicals in materials that could potentially be subject to recycling needs to be built. As of now, little is known about the actual chemical content of post-consumer and recycled textiles. Some research on PFAS content in functional and non-functional textiles has been conducted as explained in sections 2.2.3 and 2.2.4. However, very little research has been conducted on recycled non-functional textile materials and post-consumer textiles with the potential of being subject to recycling. Knowledge of these items’ chemical content has to increase to ensure safer material cycles in the future.

2.5 Analysis of PFAS in solid samples

2.5.1 Sample preparation

Most samples need a sample preparation step to remove interfering compounds, even though modern separation methods are capable of separating and quantifying analytes in complex mixtures. Sample preparation could isolate analytes, enrich the analytes, or improve their detection properties through derivatisation^[82]. Targeted PFAS analysis are usually performed using LC/MS, since liquid chromatography is best suited for the separation of PFAS. The PFAS compounds need to be extracted from the sample matrix into a suitable solution for LC/MS. All analytical results depend on a final measurement X of a physical or chemical property of the analyte, and ideally, the measurement of the property is directly proportional to the concentration, $cA = kX$ ^[83]. Extraction is the process of moving one or more compounds from their matrix to another phase, like solid samples onto a liquid, and separation isolates the analyte from potentially interfering constituents.

2.5.2 Liquid-Solid Extraction

In liquid-solid extraction (LSE) chemicals in an insoluble material can be retained in a solvent (or vice versa). The method is based on sorption/desorption properties of the analytes when in contact with different solvents. The partition of a solute between two immiscible phases is an equilibrium process that is governed by the distribution law. LSE can be coupled with Ultrasound Assisted Extraction (UAE), which uses acoustic energy that is being transmitted through the solid medium and solvents to accelerate the extraction of target compounds. The method can be assisted by a heated bath, increasing kinetics and extraction yields^[84]. The solid sample is left in a vial with solvent, extracted for approx 30 minutes, and the extract is separated from the solid residue^[85]. The matrix can be flushed with fresh solvent (which avoids re-adsorption) and go through LSE+UAE several times to optimize extraction yield, and the solvent can be expelled with pressurized nitrogen^[85]

2.5.3 Solid-Phase Extraction

Solid phase extraction (SPE) is a technique used to isolate analytes from liquid or gaseous samples. SPE uses cartridges packed with a solid phase absorbent. A hydrophobic organic compound (polar, nonpolar, moderately polar) is coated or chemically bonded to powdered silica to form the solid extraction phase. The functional groups bonded to the packing attract hydrophobic compounds in the sample by Van der Waals interactions and extracts them from the aqueous solution^[83]. A general SPE procedure is carried out by conditioning and rinsing of the sorbent, followed by application of the sample before rinsing the sorbent, and then elution of the analyte^[82].

SPE uses cartridges packed with lipophilic or lipophobic sorbents based on modified silica gel or polymers, or ion exchangers based on polymers. The technique consists of 5 steps: (1) Activation of the phase by cleaning the cartridges with elution solvent. (2) Conditioning by treating the phase with solvent in which the sample is dissolved. (3) Recovery of the analyte

from the sample solution. (4) Removal of interfering solutes by treatment with an appropriate solvent. (5) Elution of the analyte with a solvent. For steps 1-3 the cartridge should never run dry; for step 4 dryness may be necessary before the analytes are eluted in step 5. Extraction is performed by forcing the liquid through the sorbent material by means of pressure, vacuum or diffusion. The analytes are partitioned or adsorbed to the adsorbent in a manner similar to the mechanism in chromatography. The analyte can be bound to the solid phase by i.e. hydrogen bonding, dipole-dipole interactions, hydrophobic dispersion forces, and electrostatic interactions.^[85]

2.6 Instrumentation

2.6.1 Liquid Chromatography

Chromatography is a powerful and commonly used method for separating chemical components in complex mixtures. All types of chromatography takes into use a stationary phase that is fixed in place either in a column or on a planar surface, and a mobile phase that moves over or through the stationary phase. The different components of the mixture will distribute themselves between the mobile phase and the stationary phase^[83], and different interactions between the sample components and the stationary phase causes the sample components to migrate through the system at different speeds^[86]. Ideally, the differences in rates cause the components in a mixture to separate into bands along the column. Isolation of the separated species is accomplished when individual bands are eluted from the column, where they can be collected or detected^[83]. High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) uses a pump to create high pressure to move the liquid mobile phase through a column packed with a finely divided stationary phase (SP) with particle size typically 3 or 5 μm . For most HPLC the pump operates at pressures up to 400 bar, while Ultrahigh-Pressure Liquid Chromatography (UPLC) may operate between 1000- 1200 bar. The columns in the UPLC system is also packed with even smaller particles than in HPCL, down to less than 2 μm ^[82].

If a detector that responds to solute concentration is placed at the end of the column during elution and its signal is plotted as a function of time, a series of peaks is obtained. This plot is called a chromatogram, and the peak maxima can be used to identify the components of the sample for qualitative analysis while the peak areas provide measure of the amount of each species for quantitative analysis^[83]. The combination of chromatography and mass spectrometry (MS) is a widely used “tandem” technique.

2.6.2 Electrospray Ionization

Liquid chromatography and Mass Spectrometry cannot be linked directly, and an interface must be used, with its prime purpose being the removal of the chromatographic mobile phase. Electrospray Ionization (ESI) is used for compounds with polar groups that are able to accept or donate protons under given conditions, yielding positive or negative ions. The ESI process happens when the mobile phase containing the analytes enter a capillary where a high voltage is applied, typically +5 or -5 kV. A nebulizing gas (mostly N_2) is mixed to facilitate the formation of droplets. Droplets leaving the capillary are highly charged and decrease in size moving toward the entrance of the mass spectrometer. When the repulsive forces inside the drop exceed the surface tension, the droplets explodes in smaller droplets, resulting in yielding ions in the gas phase repetitively. Detection can then occur on either the protonated ions or the deprotonated ions^[82].

2.6.3 Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometry

A mass spectrometer is an instrument that produces ions, separates and detects them according to their mass-to-charge (m/z) ratio; the unitless ratio of an ions mass number m to the number

of fundamental charges z on the ion^[83].

Tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) is a technique where two mass analyzers are coupled together. One is used to isolate the ion of interest by their m/z ratio into smaller fragment ions and the other separates the fragments again by their m/z ratio and detects them^[87]. One widely used MS/MS technique is the Triple Quadrupole Mass Analyzer (QqQ), created by three sets of quadrupole rods in series. The second set of rods is used as a collision cell to focus any product ions from the fragmentation from the first set into the third set. The first and last sets of rods may be controlled to allow the transmission of ions of specific m/z ratio to give information on a desired analyte^[87]. The power of mass spectrometry lies in the fact that the mass spectra of many compounds are sufficiently specific with a high degree of confidence. The combination of the separation capability of chromatography to allow “pure” compounds to be introduced into the mass spectrometer is advantageous^[87].

2.7 Quality Assurance and Quality Control

2.7.1 Limit of Detection and Quantification

The Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantification (LOQ) are two important performance characteristics in analytical method validation. The LOD is the lowest concentration of an analyte in a sample that can be detected, but not necessarily quantified, under the method conditions, while the LOQ is the lowest concentration of an analyte in a sample that can be determined with acceptable precision and accuracy^[88]. The selectivity of a detector is its ability to determine an analyte of interest without interference from other materials present in the sample matrix or solvents used, creating “analytical noise” (also called background noise) and is often related to its LOD, i.e. the more selective it is, the lower the background noise, and consequently the lower the LOD^[87]. These limits needs to be stated, because an assay is simply not capable of accurately measuring analyte concentrations down to zero, thus sufficient analyte concentration must be present to produce an analytical signal that can reliably be distinguished from background noise^[88].

For a linear calibration curve, it is assumed that the instrument response y is linearly related to the standard concentration x in the range, expressed as $y=a+bx$ where b is the slope of the calibration curve. In this study the LOQ was determined for each target analyte by setting the limit at the lowest concentration of the standards making the calibration curve that was followed by a linear regression. The LOD was then calculated from the LOQ according to equation (2.1).

$$LOD = \frac{LOQ}{3} \quad (2.1)$$

2.7.2 Internal Standard

In the internal standard (IS) method, a known amount of a known compound is added to the sample and all calibration samples. A calibration curve is established based upon these samples, where the concentration of the analyte is varied, while the amount of IS is kept constant. An IS must be stable, available with high purity, and not present in the sample, along with having retention time close to the analyte(s) and behave like the analytes with respect to sample preparation^[82]. Ideally, each analyte needs its own IS, but this is expensive and not available for all compounds^[89]. The calibration curve is established by plotting the analyte signal versus IS signal as a function of the relative area (R_A) of analyte and IS, like in equation 2.2

$$R_A = \frac{A_{TA}}{A_{IS}} \quad (2.2)$$

Where A_{TA} is the signal of the target analyte and A_{IS} is the signal of IS. Using R_A to calculate the calibration curve and concentration of the TAs will correct for minor instrumental variations and compensate for losses of TA, making quantification more precise.

2.7.3 Recovery

Another way to estimate the bias of an analytical method is by analyzing standard reference materials (SRMs). Recovery is defined as the relative amount of analyte measured in the final extract compared to the amount in the original sample. Factors such as sample and analyte loss, cause by several reasons, lower the recovery^[82]. A recovery study can be performed using SRMs, materials that contain one or more analytes at known concentration levels. Pool samples are “spiked” with a known quantity of the chemical substance to the test sample, either before or after extraction. It can be a correction tool after analytical procedure where a considerable amount of the analyte is lost^[90]. Formulas to calculate absolute and relative recoveries is shown in equation (2.3) and (2.4).

$$\text{Absolute recovery} = \frac{A_{S\text{pike}}}{A_{\text{Matrix match}}} * 100\% \quad (2.3)$$

$$\text{Relative recovery} = \frac{RA_{S\text{pike}}}{RA_{\text{Matrix match}}} * 100\% \quad (2.4)$$

$A_{S\text{pike}}$ and $A_{\text{Matrix match}}$ is the area, while $RA_{S\text{pike}}$ and $RA_{\text{Matrix match}}$ is the relative areas (equation (2.2)) of the samples spiked before and after extraction, respectfully.

In using SRMs, it is often difficult to separate bias from ordinary random error. Reagent blank samples contain the reagents, solvents and IS used in a determination but no analyte, while sample blanks do contain the sample. All steps of the analysis are performed on the blank material. Blank determinations reveal errors due to interfering contaminants from the reagents and vessels employed in the analysis. The results are then applied as a correction to the sample measurements.

2.7.4 Matrix Effects

The presence of the sample matrix can complicate the analysis of real samples, since it can contain species with similar chemical properties as the TA and interfere with the determination of the analyte by causing an instrument response that is not easily distinguished from the analyte. Other compounds than the target analytes can also be extracted during sample analysis. These interferences are called matrix effects and can lead to undesired signal suppression or enhancement^[83] and it is shown that quantitative analysis with ESI can be substantially affected by ion-suppression or enhancement. can affect the reproducibility, linearity, and accuracy of the method^[89]. Matrix effect factor is calculated as:

$$MEF = \frac{A_{\text{matrix match}} - A_{\text{reagent blank}}}{A_{\text{standard solvent solution}}} * 100 \quad (2.5)$$

The matrix effect is calculated as shown in equation (2.6), and expressed in percentage effect

$$ME = (MEF - 1) * 100\% \quad (2.6)$$

A negative number from equation (2.6) indicates ion suppression, while a positive value indicates ion enhancement.

2.7.5 Quantification

A way to compensate for analyte differences in quantification due to matrix effects is using the matrix matched calibration method. Some samples containing a sample pool resembling the rest of the samples, are spiked with a known concentration of target analytes and internal standard before being subject to sample preparation. The concentration of the analyte in the sample can then be calculated as:

$$C_{Analyte\ in\ sample} = \frac{RA_{Sample} * C_{Spike}}{RA_{Spike}} \quad (2.7)$$

Where $C_{Analyte\ in\ sample}$ is the calculated concentration of a target analyte detected in the sample, RA_{Sample} is the relative area of the sample, C_{Spike} is the analyte concentration of the spiked samples used as matrix-matched calibration standards and RA_{Spike} is the relative area of the spiked samples. The relative areas of the reagent blanks (sample and analyte free samples) are subtracted from RA_{Sample} and RA_{Spike} before calculation of the target analyte to eliminate error due to contamination from chemical reagents or equipment used.

3 Method

3.1 Sample collection

For analyzing the presence of PFAS within textiles in the circular economy, a list of over 90 items was compiled after searching the web for various clothing items and yarn made fully or partly of recycled fibres. The list of items included recycled synthetic fibres, recycled natural fibers, and items with a mix of both. 35 items were chosen due to criteria based on price and content of recycled materials where the line was set at 50 percent recycled materials to be considered a recycled item. All textiles and yarn samples were purchased, either online or in a physical store in Trondheim, during September and October 2022. The items purchased online was not opened until they were subject for analysis in the lab. Those purchased in a physical store remained in their respective bags and were kept closed in a dark room until analysis

56 items of post-consumer textiles were collected from a reject pile doomed for export at Fretex Miljø AS, section Heggstadmyra. 30 of these were chosen for analysis with the intention to match the first batch of samples as much as possible. Extended information about the samples is shown in table A.1 in Appendix A.

Figure 3.1: The reject pile of post-consumer textiles at Fretex Heggstadmyra

3.2 Chemicals and materials

A PFAS mix consisting of 21 analytical standards (purity $\geq 98\%$, 2 ppm): PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnA, PFDODA, PFTrIDA, PFTDA, PFHxDA, PFOcDA, PFBS, PFPeS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS, PFNS, PFDS and PFDODS was purchased from Wellington Laboratories Inc. (Guelph, ON, Canada). Individual analytical standards of 21 PFAS (purity $\geq 98\%$, 100ppm): PFECHS, 4:2 FTS, 6:2 FTS, 8:2 FTS, 10:2 FTS, FOSAA, MeFOSAA, EtFOSAA, PFOSA, MeFOSA, EtFOSA, MeFOSE, EtFOSE, Gen X, ADONA, 9Cl-PF3ONS, SaMPAP and diSAMPAP was purchased from Wellington Laboratories Inc. (Guelph,

ON, Canada).

The internal standards (50 ppm) with $\geq 99\%$ purity of PFOA $^{13}\text{C}_8$, PFOS $^{13}\text{C}_8$ and 6:2 FTS $^{13}\text{C}_2$ was purchased from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories Inc. (Tewksbury, MA, USA).

Methanol (HiPerSolv Chromanorm), Ethyl Acetate (HiPerSolv Chromanorm) and Water (HiPerSolv Chromanorm) used for LC, 15 and 50 mL PP tubes were purchased from VWR Chemicals (Trondheim, Norway). A 12-port disposable liner Visiprep SPE Vacuum manifold was purchased from Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA). HybridSPE cartridges (Supelco, 30 mg bed weight, 1 mL) and disposable liners (PFTE) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Vienna, Austria). The detergent used for washing post-consumer textiles was Unik Tøyvask: Sensitiv Farget Flytende purchased from REMA 1000.

3.3 Preparation of standard solutions

An Internal Standard mixture was prepared consisting of PFOA $^{13}\text{C}_8$, PFOS $^{13}\text{C}_8$, 6:2 FTS $^{13}\text{C}_2$ and methanol. The Internal Standard solutions were originally 50 ppm for each compound. 20 μL of each standard solution and 940 μL methanol was transferred to a LC-MS glass vial to a total of 1 mL stock solution IS mixture consisting of 1 ppm of each internal standard respectively.

Two Targeted analysis mixes was used in this experiment. One consisted of 21 analytical standards with a concentration of 2 ppm. The other Targeted analysis mix was prepared in the lab consisting of 21 target analyte standards. 20 μL of 3 standard solutions with a concentration of 100 ppm and 40 μL of the standards with a concentration of 50 ppm was transferred to a LC-MS glass vial. 220 μL of methanol was also added to a total of 1 mL stock solution TA mixture with a concentration of 2 ppm of each analyte.

Standard solutions of all PFAS targeted in this experiment was prepared with concentrations of 0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50 and 100 ppb to create a calibration curve. All solutions consisted of 150 μL of water and was spiked with 6 μL of the 1ppm internal standard mixture. Necessary amounts of methanol and native standards were added to acquire the desired concentrations.

3.4 Sample pretreatment

Clothing samples were cut to approximately 5 cm x 5 cm pieces with regular scissors previously rinsed with methanol and acetone and then weighed. The cuttings were introduced in a 50 mL PP tube and the tube was filled with MilliQWater up to the 50 mL mark. In the tubes containing samples from Fretex 0.1 mL of detergent was added before the first wash (half of the recommended amount stated on the detergent flask). Detergent was used for washing the post-consumer items to remove dirt trapped in the material from use and sorting. The tubes were shaken for 15 minutes before the samples were collected using spatulas rinsed with methanol and acetone into new 50 mL PP tubes and the process was repeated two times without new addition of detergent. The samples were then taken out, covered with aluminum foil, and hung by clips in a fume hood to dry overnight. All the washing water and dried samples were carefully

labeled and kept for analysis. Samples of yarn, thread and filling was not exposed to washing. Pieces of yarn were cut with scissors rinsed with methanol and acetone from the middle layers of the skein, and a piece of the filling sample was taken from the center with tweezers rinsed with methanol and acetone to reduce the amount of dust from packaging.

(a) Beanie cut in a 5x5 cm piece

(b) Drying of samples

Figure 3.2: Stages of sample pretreatment

3.5 Sample preparation

For sample preparation development, a sample pool consisting of approximately 0.1 g of 17 different textile samples was prepared for a total of 1.909 g in a 50 ml PP tube.

Figure 3.3: Sample pool

All pieces were cut as small as possible and shaken to homogenize. This pool was used to test two different methods for the extraction of PFAS in solid samples.

3.5.1 Sample extraction for protocol 1

The first protocol was adjusted from the method used by Schellenberger et.al^[41], investigating PFAS from functional textiles.

0.1 g of the sample pool was weighted and added to a 15 ml PP tube. 20 μL of 1 ppm Internal standard and 10 μL of 2 ppm Targeted analysis mix was added to the samples. 5mL of MeOH were added to each sample. All samples were subjected to vortex prior to Liquid Solid Extraction (LSE) with ultrasonication for 30 min at 40 °C. The samples were then centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 5 minutes. The supernatant was collected and transferred into a new PP tube of 15 mL. Addition of 5 mL of MeOH and LSE with ultrasonication was repeated two more times to a final volume of approximately 15 mL of supernatant. The sample extraction concentrated under a flow of nitrogen gas and while submerged in a water bath of 35 °C to approximately 250 μL before being reconstituted in 1 mL of MeOH:MQ water (50:50) and transferred to LC vials for UPLC-ESI-QqQ-MS/MS analysis.

3.5.2 Sample extraction for protocol 2

The second protocol test was done as described by Alfred Low Boon Sin's master thesis from 2020^[91], for the extraction of PFAS in solid samples, with slight adjustments.

0.1 g of the sample pool was weighted and added to a 15 ml PP tube. 300 μL of 1M ammonium acetate, 3 mL of ethyl acetate and 20 μL of 1 ppm Internal Standard and 10 μL of Targeted Analysis mix was added according to the table above. The samples were subjected to vortex prior to LSE with ultrasonication for 45 min at 40 °C. The samples were then centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 5 minutes. The supernatant was collected and transferred to a new PP tube of 15 mL. Addition of 3 mL of ethyl acetate and LSE with ultrasonication was repeated two more times to a final volume of approximately 9 mL. 2 mL of water was added to the samples followed by vortex and centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 5 min. The supernatant of ethyl acetate was collected in a new PP tube and concentrated under nitrogen at 35 °C to approximately 250 μL before being reconstituted in 1 mL of MeOH: MQ water (50:50) and transferred to LC vials for UPLC-ESI-QqQ-MS/MS analysis.

Figure 3.4: Extracts from the pool sample using protocol 2 (after addition of 2 mL water)

3.5.3 Sample extraction for water samples

Sample preparation for water samples was done in accordance with Arvaniti's protocol for the extraction of PFAS in water samples^[92].

10 water samples collected from the third wash from the sample pretreatment were randomly chosen for analysis to investigate if PFAS is released from the textiles when washed.

50 mL of sample was adjusted to a pH of 4 with 1M of acetic acid followed by the addition of 20 μL of 1 ppm Internal Standard. The samples were then mixed with a vortex mixer prior to Solid Phase Extraction (SPE). The cartridges of the SPE (Strata X, 200mg) was conditioned with 6 mL of MeOH and 10 mL MQ water with a pH of 3. The sample was then loaded using an automated system shown in figure 3.4. After the samples had gone through the filter the cartridges were washed with 20 mL of MeOH:MQ water (40:60) and left to dry. The captured extracts in the cartridges were eluted with 4 mL of MeOH using syringes containing filters. The elution was then concentrated under a flow of nitrogen at 35°C and reconstituted in 1 mL of MeOH:MQ water (50:50). The extracts were filtered and transferred to LC vials for UPLC-QqQ-MS/MS analysis.

Figure 3.5: SPE system

3.5.4 Extraction of Textile Samples

For the analysis of the textile samples Protocol 1 described above was followed. 5 procedural blanks went through the sample treatment alongside the textile samples. 5 samples containing 0.1g of the original pool sample and spiked with 10 μL of 2 ppm Targeted Analysis mix also prepared. All samples were spiked with 20 μL of Internal Standard. If needed some samples were centrifuged again at the end of the sample treatment to remove fibers and transferred to clean vials before UPLC-QqQ-MS/MS analysis.

3.6 Quality Assurance and Quality Control

To determine the best-suited method for textile analysis, 8 samples were prepared to calculate recoveries and matrix effects and quantification according to table 3.1. All samples were prepared according to sections 3.5.1 and 3.5.2. This table was also followed for quality control of the water samples.

Table 3.1: Quality control procedure

Code	Replicates	Sample	Pre-extraction	Post-extraction
Procedural Blank	1	No	20 ppb IS	-
Blank	2	Yes	20 ppb IS	-
Spike	3	Yes	20 ppb IS, 20 ppb TA	-
Matrix matched	2	Yes	-	20ppb IS, 20ppb TA

3.7 UPLC-ESI-QqQ Analysis

The chromatographic separation was carried out using an Acquity UPLC[®] I-Class system (Waters, Milford, CT, USA) coupled to a triple quadrupole mass analyser (QqQ; Xevo TQ-S) with a ZSpray ESI ion source (Waters, Milford, CT, USA). The LC column that was used was a Kinetex C18 (30 × 2.1 mm, 1.3 μm, 100Å Phenomenex) connected to a Phenomenex guard column (C18 2.1 mm). The column temperature was set at 30 °C. The gradient elution program had two mobile phases. Water Phase (A): Water with 2 mM ammonium acetate and organic phase (B): Methanol with a flow rate of 0.25 μL/min. The gradient elution of phase A started at 80%, which was held for 0.1 min, decreased to 0% within 4.4 min which was held for 1 min, and reverted to 80% at within 0.1 min, which was held for 0.4 min, for a total run time of 6.0 min. The gradient elution for phase B started at 20% which was held for 0.2 min, increased to 100% within 4.4 min and held for 1 min, decreased to 20% within 4 min to a total run time of 6 min. The injection volume was 4 μL and the flow rate was 0.2 mL/min. The wash solvent consisted of Methanol:ultrapure water (50:50) and 0.1% formic acid. The pre-injection wash lasted for 8 seconds, and the post-injection wash lasted for 10 seconds.

The electrospray ionisation (ESI) was applied at a potential of 2 kV. The cone and source offset voltages were set at 25 and 40 V, respectively. The desolvation and cone gas flow rates were set at 650 and 150 L/h, respectively. The nebulizer gas pressure was set at 6 bar. The source and desolvation temperatures were set at 150 and 450 °C, respectively.

3.8 Data Analysis

UPLC[®]-MS/MS data and peak integrations was carried out using MassLynx v4.1 software, and quantification processing was performed with TargetLynx (Waters, Milford, CT, USA). The data was further processed with Excel (Microsoft, 2019) for descriptive statistics and making of tables and plots.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Method performance

4.1.1 Recoveries

A complete table with absolute recoveries, relative recoveries, and matrix effects of all target PFAS for the textile and water samples and their corresponding RSD values are shown in table C.1 and C.2 in Appendix C. The recoveries were calculated using equations 2.3 and 2.4 where the target analyte standard mix had a concentration of 20 ppb. Average RSD values of absolute recoveries, relative recoveries, and matrix effects for all target compounds for Protocol 1 and Protocol 2 are shown in table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Average Relative Standard Deviation (RSD) values for Absolute recoveries, Relative recoveries, and Matrix effect factors (MEF) for all target compounds in the quality control for the two protocols tested for the extraction of textile samples

	Protocol 1 (Average RSD)	Protocol 2 (Average RSD)
Absolute Recovery	0.36	0.38
Relative Recovery	0.29	0.89
Matrix Effect	0.10	0.10

The two methods tested, protocol 1 and protocol 2, both showed large varieties in absolute recoveries and relative recoveries. For protocol 1, absolute recoveries varied from 76% (for PFUnA) to 324% (for diSAMPAP). The closest to ideal recovery (100%) was performed by 6:2 FTS and PFDoDS with 101% absolute recovery. Relative recoveries varied from 86% (for FOSAA, PFBS and PFPeS) to 360% (for diSAMPAP). Disulfur decafluoride (Deca S) showed "perfect" performance at 100% relative recovery for protocol 1. Although Deca S is not a PFAS (and thus excluded from quantification) it is used to evaluate method performance, and here showed excellent relative recovery for protocol 1.

For protocol 2 absolute recovery varied from 31% (for PFHxDA) to 143% (for diSAMPAP). 6:2 FTS showed good absolute recovery performance for protocol 2 as well with 98%. The relative recoveries for protocol 2 varied from 35% for (PFHxDA) to 161% (for diSAMPAP), the same as for P1. 9Cl-PF3ONS showed the best relative recoveries for protocol 2 at 99%.

Both protocols showed overall good recoveries with some exceptions, like the abnormally high absolute recovery value for diSAMPAP for protocol 1. Protocol 1 had 35 out of 41 TAs within the optimal range of 70-140% for absolute recovery, and protocol 2 had 27 out of 41 within the range for absolute recovery. When looking at relative recoveries, both protocol 1 and protocol 2 had 34 out of 41 compounds within the optimal range, however, protocol 2 had much larger variations within the relative areas as shown by an average RSD for relative recoveries at 0.82 compared to 0.29 for Protocol 1 (table 4.1). Protocol 2 had several compounds where the signal for the spiked samples showed a high variety of RSD for relative recoveries of 2.54, 3.38, 3.67, and 5.36 for PFOSA, PFUnA, MeFOSAA, and diSAMPAP, respectively. Protocol 1 did not show these high average RSD values, only one exceeding 1 for PFHxDA. The average RSD values for

absolute recovery were almost the same for both protocols, 0.36 for Protocol 1 and 0.38 for P2, even though protocol 1 had more recoveries outside of the optimal range. For protocol 2, only one spiked sample gave a signal for PFBA, and both matrix-matched samples gave signals of 0 so absolute recovery and relative recoveries were not quantifiable for this compound.

The lab had only access to three internal standards for PFAS analysis, PFOA $^{13}\text{C}_8$, PFOS $^{13}\text{C}_8$ and 6:2 FTS $^{13}\text{C}_2$. Optimal recoveries even after internal standard correction (equation 2.4) is therefore not expected for all PFAS. Ideally, all target compounds should have their own internal standard to better correct for the inefficiency of extraction or interference from the matrix, but they are not available for all compounds and are generally expensive. In protocol one, the transition from absolute recovery to relative recoveries for PFOA, PFOS and 6:2 FTS went from 86%, 89%, and 101% to 102%, 103%, and 107%. PFOA and PFOS were corrected closer to the ideal 100%, whilst 6:2 FTS was adjusted slightly more over 100% but only with 4 percentage points and is still a good recovery. This shows the benefits of using internal standards of similar structures for the correction of analyte loss.

Table 4.2: Average Relative Standard Deviation (RSD) values for Absolute recoveries, Relative recoveries, and Matrix effect factors (MEF) for all target compounds in the quality control for the water samples

	Average RSD
Absolute Recovery	0.233
Relative Recovery	0.230
Matrix Effect	0.061

Average RSD values for absolute recovery, relative recovery, and matrix effects are shown in table 4.2, and a complete table of all values are shown in table C.2 in Appendix C. For the water samples, the average RSDs for both absolute recovery and relative recoveries were below, and thus better, than both protocols tested for the textile analysis, at 0.233 for absolute recovery and 0.230 for relative recovery. The method for PFAS analysis of water samples is frequently used at the NTNU lab and has been optimized, while PFAS analysis on textile samples has not been done at this lab before, so improvements can be made. However, both absolute and relative recoveries were generally lower in the analysis of the water samples as opposed to the textile analysis. Absolute recoveries ranged from 3% (for diSAMPAP) to 86% (for Gen X) and relative recoveries ranged from 5% (for diSAMPAP) to 128% (for PFNA). 28 out of 43 values of absolute recoveries and 19 values for relative recoveries were outside the optimal range of 70-140%, all below 70%. Different extraction methods were used for the water samples, SPE in contrast to LSE with ultrasonication, impacting risks of analyte loss. The target analytes in the water samples had to pass both the SPE cartridges and syringes with a filter, where some might be trapped. Some target compounds like SAMPAP, diSAMPAP, PFHxDA, and PFOcDA had very low recoveries even after internal standard correction with relative recoveries of 5%, 20%, 15%, and 23%, respectively. Interpretation of possible detections of these compounds in the analysis should therefore be done with caution.

4.1.2 Matrix effects

A complete table of calculated matrix effects for the textile samples and the water samples are shown together with recovery values in table C.1 and C.2 in Appendix C. An average RSDs based on the matrix effect for each target compound is shown in table 4.1 and 4.2. Matrix-matched samples were prepared in the sample preparation for each protocol by spiking two samples containing the sample pool with 20 ppb of target analyte standards after extraction, and their areas were used to calculate MEF and ME according to equation 2.5 and 2.6.

Most target analytes exhibited negative ME values for both of the protocols tested for the analysis of PFAS in textiles. 36 of our 41 and 32 out of 41 for protocol 1 and protocol 2, respectively, suggesting that interfering compounds extracted from the textile samples, or contamination, contributed to ion suppression and lower detection of these target analytes by the mass spectrometer. ME values ranged from 58% to -96% for protocol 1 (with the exception of PFBA) and from 83% to -100% for protocol 2. The ME value for PFBA for protocol 1 was calculated to be 595% and can be considered an outlier. For this compound, one of the blank samples from protocol 1 gave a relatively high signal of 3968 while the matrix-matched samples gave signals of 6683 and 3415. In addition, the PFBA signal from the standard containing 20 ppb of each target analyte, gave a very low signal, flipping the weight of the equation to give an abnormally high ME percentage value. For protocol 2, the two matrix-matched samples had values of 0 for PFBA, giving a ME percentage value of -100%. This method test was therefore unable to suggest the impacts matrix effects had on the quantification of PFBA. This could have been caused by a mistake during sample preparation or instrumental error.

By combining the data for recoveries and matrix effect for the two tested protocols, and comparing the average RSD values (table 4.1), protocol 1 was chosen to be used for the PFAS quantification of the textile samples. The relative recoveries were the determining factor for this choice. Since protocol 1 was chosen it must be noted that along with the outlying matrix effects of PFBA; EtFOSA, EtFOSAA, PFD_oDA, diSAMPAP, PFTDA, PFH_xDA, and, PFO_cDA had quite drastic matrix effect values of -86%, -84%, -84%, -90%, -87%, -95%, and -96%, respectively. Detections for these should be interpreted with caution, even if the quantification method used accounts for these variations by using the relative area of spiked samples since many target analytes differ structurally from the internal standards used to correct for interferences.

The calculations of matrix effects for the water samples (Table C.2, in appendix C) showed 23 negative values and 19 positive (ME for PFO_cDA was not quantifiable due to no signal from the matrix-matched samples) and the range was from -99 to 35. The average RSD of 0.061 is lower than for the textile samples at 0.10, which is expected because water is a less complex matrix than the extract from textiles. 7H-PFH_pA had the highest detected matrix effect of -99%, but its absolute and relative recoveries were well within the optimal range: 81 % and 109%, respectively.

4.1.3 LOD and LOQ

The limits of quantification were determined by investigating the calibration curves for each target compound where the lowest concentration of the calibration curve with a sufficient peak signal was followed by a linear regression made by increasing concentrations was chosen. The LOD was then determined using equation 2.1. The values are presented in table 4.3 and 4.4.

Table 4.3: Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantification (LOQ) in ng/mL for each targeted PFAS for the textile samples

Compound	LOD (ng/ml)	LOQ (ng/ml)
Deca S	0.02	0.05
Gen X	0.67	2.00
PFPeA	0.03	0.10
PFHxA	0.03	0.10
4:2 FTS	0.02	0.05
7H-PFHpA	0.02	0.05
NaDONA	0.00	0.01
PFOA	0.07	0.20
6:2 FTS	0.07	0.20
PFHpS	0.01	0.02
PFNA	0.01	0.02
P37DMOA	0.00	0.01
PFOSA	0.01	0.02
PFOS	0.02	0.05
MeFOSA	0.00	0.01
PFDA	0.02	0.05
EtFOSA	0.00	0.01
EtFOSAA	0.00	0.01
8:2 FTS	0.02	0.05
9Cl-PF3ONS	0.01	0.02
FOSAA	0.17	0.50
PFUnA	0.17	0.50
MeFOSAA	0.02	0.05
EtFOSE	0.17	0.50
PFDoDA	0.17	0.50
MeFOSE	0.17	0.50
10:2 FTS	0.03	0.10
PFTriDA	0.17	0.50
diSAMPAP	6.67	20.00
PFTDA	0.17	0.50
PFHxDA	0.07	0.20
PFBA	3.33	10.00
PFBS	0.00	0.01
PFPeS	0.01	0.02
PFHpA	0.02	0.05
PFHxS	0.02	0.05
PFECHS	0.00	0.01
PFNS	0.02	0.05
PFDS	0.00	0.01
SaMPAP	3.33	10.00
PFDoDS	0.00	0.01

Table 4.4: Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantification (LOQ) in ng/mL for each targeted PFAS for the water samples

	LOD (ng/mL)	LOQ (ng/mL)
Deca S	0.17	0.5
Gen X	0.17	0.5
PFPeA	0.17	0.5
PFHxA	0.07	0.2
4:2 FTS	0.03	0.1
7H-PFHpA	0.03	0.1
NaDONA	0.03	0.1
PFOA	0.03	0.1
6:2 FTS	0.03	0.1
PFHpS	0.03	0.1
PFNA	0.03	0.1
P37DMOA	0.03	0.1
PFOSA	0.03	0.1
PFOS	0.03	0.1
MeFOSA	0.03	0.1
PFDA	0.03	0.1
EtFOSA	0.03	0.1
EtFOSAA	0.03	0.1
8:2 FTS	0.03	0.1
9Cl-PF3ONS	0.03	0.1
FOSAA	0.03	0.1
PFUnA	0.03	0.1
MeFOSAA	0.03	0.1
EtFOSE	0.07	0.2
PFDoDA	0.03	0.1
MeFOSE	0.03	0.1
10:2 FTS	0.07	0.2
PFTriDA	0.03	0.1
diSAMPAP	0.03	0.1
PFTDA	0.03	0.1
PFHxDA	0.03	0.1
PFBS	0.03	0.1
PFPeS	0.03	0.1
PFHpA	0.03	0.1
PFHxS	0.03	0.1
PFECHS	0.03	0.1
PFNS	0.03	0.1
PFDS	0.03	0.1
PFDoDS	0.03	0.1
PFOcDA	0.33	1

For the textile samples, the lowest possible LOQ was 0.01 ng/ml as it was the lowest concentration of the calibration standards. Many compounds were assigned a LOD of 0.01 ng/ml, demonstrating high sensitivity of the instrument down to 0.01 ppb. However, high LOQs were set for diSAMPAP at 20 ng/ml and PFBA and SAMPAP both at 10 ng/ml, since they did not exhibit linear regression at lower concentrations. Variations and minor faults in the instrument could be a reason for inadequate signals for all target PFAS sub 1 ppb.

The calibration standards made for the water samples started at a concentration of 0.1 ppb, making the lowest possible LOQ 0.1 ng/ml. Most compounds received a LOQ of 0.1 ng/ml except Deca S, Gen X, PFPeA, PFHxA EtFOSE, 10:2 FTS, and PFOcDA with limits of 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2 and 1, respectively. This method had overall good sensitivity performance, without the larger exemptions observed for the textile quantification. SAMPAP, diSAMPAP, and, PFBA had quantification limits of 0.1 ng/ml for the water samples contrary to the high LOQs for the water samples, showing that the instrument is capable of detecting these compounds down to 1 ppb, even for the more complex structures of SAMPAP and diSAMPAP.

4.2 Occurrence of target PFAS in textiles

Detection frequencies, median, average, minimum and average concentrations of 38 target analytes in ng/g for all samples (n=67) are shown in table 4.5. The same parameters with the unit ng/cm² is presented in table 4.6. Notice the difference in the number of samples for the two tables (n=67 and n=50), which results in lower detection frequency for some target PFAS for table 4.6 with the ng/cm² unit. The unit ng/cm² was determined to better compare with existing literature that often uses the weight of detected PFAS per area of fabric. 15 samples in this study in the recycled category were yarn, 1 was a thread and 1 was filling, and not practically quantifiable for surface area and thus not included in table 4.6. TriDeFHxSA and PFOcDA were two of the targeted PFAS in the method but were deleted from the data set due to bad chromatograms creating inadequate calibration curves for the determination of LOQ and LOD.

Table 4.5: Detection frequency, median, average (Avg.), minimum (Min.) and maximum (Max.) concentrations of 39 target analytes in ng/g for all samples (n=67). Values below LOD is excluded

Compound	Detection frequency (%)	Med. (ng/g)	Avg. (ng/g)	Min. (ng/g)	Max. (ng/g)
PFCAs					
Short chain					
PFBA	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
PFPea	9	2.79	7.59	0.67	32.53
PFHxA	12	17.33	28.05	2.46	94.59
Long-chain					
PFHpA	9	1.57	1.84	0.80	3.34
PFOA	18	2.31	2.47	0.81	4.38
PFNA	15	0.89	2.04	0.24	10.64
PFDA	4	0.79	8.42	0.74	23.73
PFUnA	3	3.23	3.23	1.79	4.68
PFDoDA	4	4.28	4.87	2.10	8.22
PFTriDa	3	2.34	2.34	2.15	2.53
PFTDA	6	2.34	2.69	1.67	4.39
PFHxDA	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
P37DMOA	15	0.12	0.30	0.04	1.78
7H-PFHpA	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
PFSAs					
Short chain					
PFBS	1	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
PFPeS	21	0.57	0.93	0.16	2.79
Long-chain					
PFHxS	16	0.49	0.83	0.33	2.65
PFHpS	12	0.59	2.40	0.11	9.59
PFOS	57	0.68	1.26	0.16	12.22
PFDoDS	45	11.79	11.75	0.26	36.13
PFECHS	21	0.12	0.13	0.03	0.40
FTSs					
4:2 FTS	9	0.42	9.19	0.19	32.73
6:2 FTS	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
8:2 FTS	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
10:2 FTS	1	0.46	0.46	0.46	0.46
FOSAAs					
FOSAA	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
MeFOSAA	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
EtFOSAA	25	0.08	0.11	0.04	0.21
FOSAs					
PFOSA	9	0.15	0.76	0.07	3.32
MeFOSA	12	0.16	0.18	0.04	0.42
EtFOSA	13	0.30	0.30	0.04	0.57
FOSEs					
MeFOSE	7	19.41	17.07	1.96	38.92
EtFOSE	1	1.93	1.93	1.93	1.93
Fluoropolymers					
Gen X	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
NaDONA	1	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
9Cl-PF3ONS	21	0.11	0.18	0.06	1.11
SaMPAPs					
SAMPAP	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
diSAMPAP	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d

Table 4.6: Detection frequency (DF), median (Med.), average (Avg.), minimum (Min.) and maximum (Max.) concentrations of 39 target analytes for a selection of samples (n=50). Samples of yarn/thread/filling are excluded due to the inability of quantifying the sample area in ng/cm², along with values below LOD.

Compound	DF (%)	Med. (ng/cm ²)	Avg. (ng/cm ²)	Min. (ng/cm ²)	Max. (ng/cm ²)
PFCA s					
Short chain					
PFBA	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
PFPea	7	0.261	0.319	0.022	0.941
PFHxA	10	0.306	0.922	0.050	3.025
Long-chain					
PFHpA	7	0.039	0.085	0.021	0.234
PFOA	16	0.063	0.138	0.015	0.418
PFNA	15	0.039	0.064	0.006	0.187
PFDA	3	0.199	0.199	0.015	0.384
PFUnA	1	0.076	0.076	0.076	0.076
PFDoDA	4	0.133	0.209	0.120	0.374
PFTriDa	1	0.035	0.035	0.035	0.035
PFTDA	6	0.037	0.080	0.031	0.215
PFHxDA	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
P37DMOA	13	0.004	0.008	0.001	0.029
7H-PFHpA	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
PFSA s					
Short chain					
PFBS	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
PFPeS	16	0.024	0.027	0.005	0.094
Long-chain					
PFHxS	12	0.016	0.044	0.007	0.195
PFHpS	10	0.016	0.059	0.002	0.234
PFOS	43	0.022	0.084	0.005	1.187
PFDoDS	39	0.331	0.406	0.026	1.291
PFECHS	15	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.005
FTS s					
4:2 FTS	4	0.019	0.156	0.005	0.445
6:2 FTS	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
8:2 FTS	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
10:2 FTS	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
FOSAA s					
FOSAA	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
MeFOSAA	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
EtFOSAA	25	0.003	0.003	0.001	0.006
FOSA s					
PFOSA	9	0.009	0.015	0.001	0.054
MeFOSA	10	0.004	0.008	0.001	0.040
EtFOSA	13	0.007	0.013	0.001	0.054
FOSE s					
MeFOSE	3	0.178	0.178	0.160	0.195
EtFOSE	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
Fluoropolymers					
Gen X	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
NaDONA	1	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
9Cl-PF3ONS	21	0.002	0.004	0.001	0.021
SaMPAP s					
SAMPAP	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
diSAMPAP	0	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d

Table 4.5 represents the entire sample batch and can give an indication of levels of PFAS detection on textiles of different fibres in attire where PFAS is not expected to have been added. Out of 38 target PFAS, 28 was detected in at least one sample. PFBA, PFHxDA, PFOcDA, 7H-PHpA, 6:2 FTS, 8:2 FTS, FOSAA, MeFOSAA, Gen X, SaMPAP and diSaMPAP was not detected above the LOD in any samples. PFOS had the highest detection frequency of 57% followed by PFDoDS with 45%. The concentration range of detected target PFAS was 0.04 - 94.59 ng/g and 0.001 - 3.025 ng/cm². The sample with the highest detected concentration of a single target PFAS was 94.59 ng/g of PFHxA in a post-consumer swimwear item. PFHxA had relatively high overall detection with a median value of 17.33 ng/g, the second highest median value after MeFOSE with 19.41. PFHxA also had the highest average value of 28.05 due to a few of the detected values being relatively high compared to other PFAS that for the most part were below 5 ng/g.

Only 3 out of the 67 samples had zero detection of any target PFAS, including underwear made of 100% recycled polyester, thread made of 83% recycled polyamide and 17% elastane, and ribbon made of 90% recycled cotton and 10% other recycled fibers. The rest of the samples (96%) had at least one detection of a target PFAS. Concentrations of each target PFAS detected in the samples were summed together, and the amount of total PFAS in the entire sample batch ranged from 0.05 - 98.29 ng/g and 0.001 - 3.338 ng/cm². The sample with the highest detection frequency of target PFAS was a pair of children's swim shorts with 12 detected PFAS and total PFAS concentrations of 64.30 ng/g and 1.041 ng/cm². The sample with the highest value of total PFAS was a post-consumer swimwear item with concentrations of 98.29 ng/g and 1.897 ng/cm². PFHxA amounted to this total with 94.59 ng/g and 1.826 ng/cm², over 96% for both units. The sample with the most amount of PFAS per unit area of 3.338 ng/cm² was a children's facemask made of 100% recycled polyester. Also here PFHxA amounted to over 90% of the total PFAS value. Extended sample information is shown in table A.1, and concentrations for all target PFAS are shown in table D.1-D.7 in Appendix D.

4.2.1 Comparison of recycled and post-consumer textiles

Box and whisker plots based on total PFAS concentrations (ng/g) in all 67 samples is presented in figure 4.1, and for 50 samples converted to the unit ng/cm² in figure 4.2 (the difference in number of samples is explained in section 4.2). The plots are split into two series representing the purchased samples made of recycled materials named “Recycled” and those collected from Fretex labeled “Post-consumer”. The boxes show the distribution of data from the lower to the upper quartile, the lines extending vertically represent the minimum and maximum values, unless outliers exist that will be placed as dots outside those lines. The mean is represented by the X, while the median is the line inside the boxes.

Figure 4.1: Box and whisker plot presenting total PFAS concentrations of all samples (n=67) in ng/g divided into two series, textile samples made with recycled materials (n=37) and post-consumer textiles (n=30)

As shown in Figure 4.1, total PFAS concentrations were detected consecutively higher in the post-consumer textiles. The total PFAS concentrations in the data set for post-consumer textiles have higher median (16.82 ng/g) and average values (21.76 ng/g) than the recycled textiles (median = 3.32 ng/g, average = 9.35 ng/g). The upper quartile of the recycled textiles range is even below the lower quartile of the post-consumer textiles range, illustrating the difference. The recycled textiles range does have more outliers above the box, but the highest total PFAS concentration is found in a post-consumer item. No outliers are below either of the boxes, since relatively low values were the norm, especially for the recycled textiles, and higher total PFAS values the exception. Even though the data set for recycled textiles had three more outliers than the data set for post-consumer textiles, the general trend is that the total PFAS concentration

is greater for post-consumer textiles than recycled textiles for the targeted PFAS included in the method.

Figure 4.2: Box and whisker plot presenting total concentrations of selected samples ($n=37$) in ng/cm^2 divided into two series, textile samples made with recycled materials ($n=20$) and post consumer textiles ($n=30$). The total concentrations was calculated by addition of the concentrations of each target PFAS in each sample.

Figure 4.2 displaying total PFAS concentrations in ng/cm^2 show more similar distributions than figure 4.1. This is due to both the unit conversion making the ranges more narrow and the exclusion of 17 recycled textile samples, pushing the upper and lower quartiles further out in the data set. This is also illustrated with the recycled textiles series only having one outlier in figure 4.2, but 4 in figure 4.1. The median and average values for the post-consumer series (median = 0.379, average = 0.617) is still higher than for the recycled textiles series (median = 0.181, average = 0.508), but the difference between the two is not as clear as in figure 4.1. With the exception of some excluded samples with higher total PFAS values of 15.84 - 72.53 ng/g , most excluded samples (yarn/thread/filling) had very low values. 13 of these had values below 7 ng/g and 9 below 1 ng/g , also contributing to moving the distribution for the recycled series up closer to the distribution for the post-consumer textiles series.

Since these items were not advertised as stain-oil- or water-repellent it is assumed that no PFAS were intentionally added in textile finishing during manufacturing. These PFAS then need to have made their way to the textiles through contamination. Possible sources are PFAS used as processing aids in dyeing or lubrication on machinery and equipment in textile processing^[1]. Recycled textiles can have been subject to this type of contamination both the first and second

time the fiber was manufactured. PFAS that might have been present in the original textiles could have remained after being subject to mechanical recycling, or PFAS could have previous plastic products that are often used to make synthetic fabrics^[1] labeled as “recycled”. Other sources of contamination could also stem from storage^[58], which is relevant for both types of textiles. Post-consumer textiles could in addition to manufacturing have been in contact with PFAS in the use phase, with regular wear and tear and environmental and human interference^[58].

Four samples in this study were labeled as made from post-consumer denim jeans as opposed to scraps from textile production; sample REC_25, REC_26, REC_28, and REC_32 with total PFAS concentrations of 5.54, 4.22, 6.40, and 3.32 ng/g, respectively. These values are not in the top range of detected PFAS values for recycled samples, but interestingly the values are close in range as opposed to the range for all recycled textiles samples from n.d - 72.53 ng/g. No post-consumer denim jeans were analyzed that could act as a comparison for yarn made of this type of material to see how much and what type of PFAS might transfer.

4.2.2 Distribution of different groups of PFAS in textiles

The detection frequencies for recycled textiles and post-consumer textiles of different groups of PFAS is shown in table 4.7. PFAAs are split into short- and long-chain PFCAs and PFSAs with the rest of the targeted PFAS put in the category “Other PFAS”. Composition graphs displaying the distribution of the same groups based on the total PFAS concentrations in ng/g for the recycled and post-consumer textiles are shown in figure 4.3.

Table 4.7: Detection frequencies for recycled textiles (n=37) and post-consumer textiles (n=30), divided into four groups, PFCAs (long and short chain), PFSAs (long and short chain) and other PFASs.

Chain-length:	PFCAs		PFSAs		Other PFASs	All PFASs
	Short	Long	Short	Long		
Recycled	22 %	38 %	11 %	84 %	54 %	92%
Post-consumer	17 %	50 %	33 %	93 %	77 %	100 %

Figure 4.3: Composition of different groups of PFAS for all recycled textiles (n=37) and post-consumer textiles (n=30) based on the detected PFAS concentration (ng/g)

100% of the post-consumer textiles and 92% of the recycled textiles had detections of at least one target PFAS (table 4.7). The most frequently detected PFAS group for both the recycled and post-consumer textiles was long-chain PFSAs with DF of 84% and 93%, respectively. For all PFAS-groups except short-chain PFCAs, the post-consumer textiles had higher detection frequencies than the recycled textiles.

One similarity between the recycled and post-consumer textiles in their overall composition of PFAS groups, is that short-chain PFASs was found to contribute the least amount to the total PFAS concentrations in the samples. The contributions for recycled textiles follow the order short-chain PFCAs > other PFASs > long-chain PFCAs > long-chain PFASs > short-chain PFASs, whilst the post-consumer textiles follow the order long-chain PFASs > short-chain PFCAs > other PFAS > long-chain PFCAs > short-chain PFASs.

A stand-out result is that long-chain PFASs contributed a significant amount to the high detection frequencies and total PFAS concentration for post-consumer textiles. This is due to the high detection frequency and concentrations of PFOS and PFDoDS. PFOS had a detection frequency of 57% and contributed 14.75 ng/g while PFDoDS had a detection frequency of 80% and contributed 324.97 ng/g of the total long-chain PFASs concentration of 385 ng/g for post-consumer textiles. EtFOsa also had a high detection frequency for the post-consumer textile samples of 53%, but only contributed with 2.32 ng/g to the total concentration of "other PFAS".

PFOS was also frequently detected in the recycled textile samples with a detection frequency of 57% (the same as for post-consumer samples), and had mostly concentrations of the same magnitude. Contrary to the findings for post-consumer textiles, PFDoDS was only detected in 16% of the recycled textile samples, where some was of the same magnitude and others much lower. This shows a clear difference in occurrence of this compound between the two types of textile samples. Since it was detected in so many post-consumer textiles cross-contamination between these samples could be suggested as a cause. They were all picked from one big pile in a warehouse at Fretex's collection station, so cross-contamination could have happened from the environment they were all handled in during sorting. Another tentative explanation could be that one item containing high amounts of PFDoDS (or its precursor) had been in contact with the samples. But this type of residue contamination should be easily washable, and since all post-consumer textile samples were subject to three rounds of washing this is not likely. Traces of long-chain PFASs could have transferred to the textiles during manufacturing, and since long-chain PFAAs was more frequently used in the past, this could be an explanation to the dominance of this type of PFAS in post-consumer textiles, as opposed to more use of short-chain PFAAs now.

4.2.3 Comparison of different material types

Median concentrations of total PFAS grouped in the same way as section 4.2.2 of three different material types is shown in figure 4.4. Natural materials refer to samples of wool or cotton, synthetic materials refer to samples made of one or more of the following: polyester, elastane, polyamide, acrylic, and spandex. Mixed materials refer to samples containing both natural and synthetic materials (one sample made partly of viscose and other synthetic fibers is put in the mixed category, as viscose is based on cellulose and is considered a natural material).

Figure 4.4: Median concentrations of grouped PFAS for three different material types; natural materials (n=26) synthetic materials (n=24) and mixed materials (n=6). Post-consumer samples without labels or unreadable labels were excluded.

Samples of synthetic materials gave a median concentration of short-chained PFCAs about double that of natural materials and about ten times that of mixed materials. Synthetic materials also had median concentrations of “other PFAS” several magnitudes higher than the natural and mixed materials. Big differences were not seen for the other PFAS categories. The sample size of mixed material was quite low (n=6) compared to the other types (n=26 and n=24), giving poorer representation of this material.

Table 4.8: Median concentrations (ng/g) of grouped PFAS in three categories of materials. Natural materials; recycled (n=17), and post-consumer (n=9). Synthetic materials; recycled (n=16), and post-consumer (n=8). Mixed materials; recycled (n=4), and post-consumer (n=2). Post-consumer samples without labels or unreadable labels were excluded.

	PFCAs		PFASs		Other PFASs	Total
	hort-chain	Long-chain	Short-chain	Long-chain		
<i>Natural materials</i>						
Recycled	3.74	4.32	0.66	0.62	2.46	11.79
Post consumer	28.94	0.58	13.70	13.70	0.48	57.40
<i>Synthetic materials</i>						
Recycled	6.08	3.64	1.64	0.62	3.43	15.41
Post consumer	15.66	1.28	0.43	10.01	0.45	27.83
<i>Mixed materials</i>						
Recycled	0.69	2.52	n.d	0.37	0.09	3.66
Post consumer	n.d	0.26	n.d	14.21	0.28	14.74

In table 4.8 the data on different types of material is further divided up into recycled and post-consumer textiles. As shown in section 4.2.1 and 4.2.2 as well, the post-consumer textiles had overall higher concentrations of all PFAS, and the split into different materials did not change this. However, for some categories, the recycled textile samples have higher median values than the post-consumer textiles. In samples of natural materials, recycled textiles have higher median values for long-chain PFCAs and “other PFAS”. This is the case also for samples of synthetic materials along with short-chain PFASs.

For recycled natural materials contamination of PFAS could have happened by use of PFAS-containing processing aids the first or second time it was manufactured, or when going through mechanical recycling into new fiber. Contamination of synthetic material could arise during manufacturing of the textiles, but could also have been added to the plastic product it was derived from^[1], which has been “recycled” into new textile fiber.

4.3 Occurrence of target compounds in washing water

Detection frequencies, median, average, minimum and maximum concentrations of targeted PFAS found in 10 water samples obtained from the third wash of the textile samples during sample pre-treatment are presented in table 4.9. Target PFAS that was not detected is excluded from this table. Calculated concentrations for each sample are shown in table B.1 in Appendix B.

Table 4.9: Detection frequency (DF), median (Med.), average (Avg.), minimum (Min.) and maximum (Max.) concentrations in ng/ml of 10 water samples (third wash). 4 of the samples are from the washing of recycled textiles, and 6 is from the washing of post-consumer textiles

Compound	DF (%)	Med. (ng/ml)	Avg. (ng/ml)	Min. (ng/ml)	Max. (ng/ml)
PFCA_s					
Short chain					
PFPeA	20	0.069	0.069	<LOQ	0.069
Long-chain					
7H-PFHpA	30	0.034	0.074	0.028	0.159
PFSA_s					
Short chain					
PFBS	10	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.009
PFPeS	20	0.011	0.011	<LOQ	0.011
Long-chain					
PFOS	50	0.017	0.017	<LOQ	0.017
PFDS	40	0.006	0.020	0.002	0.064
PFDoDS	30	0.054	0.056	0.038	0.074
PFECHS	10	0.008	0.008	0.008	0.008
FTS_s					
4:2 FTS	20	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
6:2 FTS	70	0.005	0.011	<LOQ	0.036
FOSAA_s					
MeFOSAA	10	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
EtFOSAA	20	0.002	0.002	<LOQ	0.002
FOSA_s					
EtFOSA	20	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
MeFOSA	10	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ
SaMPAP_s					
diSAMPAP	100	0.009	0.018	0.003	0.076

diSAMPAP was detected in all 10 water samples even though it was not detected in any textile samples. The LOD for diSAMPAP was one of the highest of all compounds in the textile analysis, but the water analysis could give an indication that it does exist in several of the textiles nevertheless. However, as mentioned in section 4.1.1 diSAMPAP had low absolute and relative recoveries, so the real concentrations of diSAMPAP might differ substantially from the reported concentrations. Still, since this compound was detected in all of the water samples with good sensitivity of the instrument (LOQ of 0.1 ng/ml, table 4.4), and the quantification method accounts for matrix effects, it is accurate to state that this compound was present in the water samples. 6:2 FTS was also detected in water samples with a DF of 70%, even though the analysis of the textiles did not detect this compound. PFOS has a detection frequency of

50% similar to that of the textile analysis of 58% (the highest detection frequency for the textile samples).

The second highest detected compound of the textile analysis, PFDoDS, was detected in 3 water samples but did not show higher frequency or concentration in the water used to wash the post-consumer textiles, but the calculated concentrations of PFDoDS in water were some of the highest concentrations with a range of 0.054 - 0.074 ng/ml. 7H-PFHpA had the highest detected concentration in the water samples at 0.159 ng/ml. This a surprising finding considering it was not detected in the textile samples with a LOD of 0.05 ng/ml. PFOA, a previously common additive in surfactant and DWR technology was not detected in the water samples. Due to PFOA's persistence and ubiquitous detection in the environment as a result of heavy production in the past, it was surprising that PFOA was not detected in the washing water. Detected compounds in these water samples could be residue from packaging or dirt particles removed from the post-consumer textiles, in addition to PFAS that is present in the textiles from manufacturing.

Table 4.10: Ratios calculated by dividing the concentrations in textile samples (ng/g) by the concentrations in corresponding washing water samples (ng/ml).

Sample	PFOS	EtFOSAA	PFDoDS
FX-4		0.030	
FX-15	0.015		0.002
FX-30			0.004

The concentrations of the 10 textile samples that were subject to washing with the water samples for this analysis were divided by the concentrations of their corresponding water samples, and those that resulted in a value is shown in table 4.10. Only 4 data points of detected target PFAS in the textiles had corresponding detection in the water samples (excluding those that had no detection), showing a lack of correlation in target PFAS being detected in textiles and water it has been subject to during washing. Interestingly though, the data points obtained in table 4.10 comes from a relatively high detection of the target PFAS in each sample, compared to the other samples. Of the 10 textile samples discussed in this section, FX-15 had the highest detection of PFOS and PFDoDS where detection in the washing water was also detected.

Even though no clear correlation was seen between the analysis of the textiles and the washing water, this shows that PFAS is released from textiles when subjected to washing, which has been shown in previous studies for functional textiles^[93], along with the release of PFAAs from weathering^{[41][40]}, where the suggested mechanism is the degradation of precursors and loss of textile fibers/particles from DWR coating.

4.4 Comparison with literature

The method used in this study was unable to detect many commonly used PFAS in the textiles industry like PASF-based derivatives and fluorotelomers^[27]. However, these are known precursors to PFCAs and PFSAs, that had high detection frequencies (table 4.5). The most studied PFAS group is the PFAAs, including the two most studied PFAS; PFOA and PFOS and this is also the case for investigations of ionic PFAS in functional textiles. PFAAs are the group that is most expected to be present, due to their wide use in industry, including their precursors^[27], which is also shown in this study, with high detection frequencies across the sample batch dominated by PFSAs (table 4.5). Side-chained fluorinated polymers using PFBS have been used in the textile industry, but here PFBS was only detected in one sample. Other types of PFAS that have been found in functional textiles are FASAs, ETFASEs, FTOH and FToflins, FTSAs, and side-chained fluorinated polymers using PTFE, but the method in this study was unable to detect these types.

Most studies that have investigated the occurrence and levels of PFAS in textiles have done so in functional textiles that have been subjected to textile finishing, but some have also included non-functional textiles often focusing on children and infant clothes. A selection of studies investigating PFAS in attire with the detected concentration ranges is shown in table 4.11.

Table 4.11: Concentrations in various textiles from previous studies and this study divided into two units: ng/cm² and ng/g

Year and sampling location	Product type	Total Ionic PFAS	Total FTOHs	Ref.
Unit = ng/cm²				
2006, Scandinavia	Outdoor gear	0.233 - 45.2	n.d - 1070	[36]
2015, Denmark	Children's products	0.01-4.53		[42]
2016, Thailand	Home textiles, personal attire, and outdoor gear	0.002 - 1.414		[39]
2017, US	Outdoor gear	0.066 - 5.592	n.d - 1400	[43]
2017, US	Children's clothing	n.d	n.d - 13	[43]
2020, Sweden	Outdoor gear	n.d - 8.29	n.d - 12	[40]
2021, US & Canada	Children's products	0.0004 - 0.818	n.d - 38100	[34]
2021, US & Canada	Children's uniforms	0.0014-0.798	n.d - 38100	[34]
2020, US	Outdoor gear	n.d - 2.29		[45]
2020, US	Infant clothing	n.d - 0.481		[45]
2023, Europe	Non-functional textiles	0.001 - 3.025		This study
Unit = ng/g				
2009, US	Children's uniform	90.3 - 672		[44]
2014, US	Children's uniform	n.d - 976		[38]
2020, US	Infant clothing	n.d - 21.5		[45]
2020, US	Outdoor gear	n.d - 12.9		[37]
2020, US	Infant clothing	Median: 3.42	Median: 27.1	[37]
2021, US & Canada	Children's products	0.021-48.8	n.d - 153 000	[34]
2021, US & Canada	Children's uniforms	0.10-34.6 ng/g	n.d - 153 000	[34]
2023, Europe	Non-functional textiles	0.4 - 94.59		This study

Overall the detection range of targeted PFAS in this study is comparable to values presented in previous studies testing non-functional textiles. Concentrations levels were very similar to two previous studies screening children's products and clothing in Denmark and the US^{[42] [34]} in regards to targeted PFAS analysis, and higher than a screening of children's clothing in the US which detected no target PFAS in children products^[43]. Several studies have investigated PFAS concentrations in children's uniforms, where two studies from 2009^[44] and 2014^[38] had much larger ranges than detected in this study, whilst the recent study from 2021 which tested uniforms labeled as stain-repellent had a comparable range to this project^[34].

PFAS concentrations found by previous studies investigating functional textiles are as expected higher than for non-functional textiles, since PFAS are usually added for water-, oil- and stain-repellence. Nevertheless, ranges of ionic PFAS detected in functional textiles like outdoor gear in some previous studies have comparable ranges to this project^{[39][43][45][37]}, although most were at the lower end of this range. Outdoor gear and treated apparel is often coated with side-chain fluorinated polymer with backbones containing PFAAs, precursors of PFAAs, so detection of PFAAs on functional attire is usually caused by degradation.

Often the highest detections of PFAS in functional textiles are caused by the detection of PFAA precursors such as FTOHs. The recent investigation of school uniforms, outdoor wear, and miscellaneous items from North America for children using PIGE and targeted PFAS analysis^[34] found that the PFAS content in school uniforms was almost entirely dominated by 6:2 FTOH, representing 98% of the total targeted PFAS concentration. In all products, ionic PFAS, including PFCAs and PFSAs, were detected but contributed less than 5% of the total targeted PFAS concentration. Several other studies have shown this domination of FTOH over PFAAs in both functional and non-functional clothing, including children's products^{[43][35][36]}. Even though the method in this thesis project was not able to detect PFAS precursors such as FTOHs, there is reason to believe they were present on some of the tested textiles due to recurring evidence that if concentrations of ionic PFAS within the ranges in table 4.11 is detected, concentrations of FTOHs could be several magnitudes higher.

Some of these studies also demonstrated the shift in the industry towards the use of shorter-chained PFAS by higher detections of 6:2 FTOH^{[40][43]} in textiles purchased after 2012 than 8:2 FTOHs for those purchased before 2012^{[78][36]}. Figure 4.3 shows that short-chained PFCAs contribute more to the overall composition of the recycled textile samples, than the post-consumer samples. The same trend cannot be seen for short-chain PFSAs, as this group contributed the least out of all to the composition of PFAS for both types of samples, and the detection frequency for this PFAS group was higher for post-consumer samples. The domination of long-chain PFSAs in post-consumer samples could be a result of the shift in the industry where the non-functional post-consumer textiles can have been contaminated by long-chain PFSAs used as manufacturing aids before they were restricted. Recycled textiles contained over 40% short-chain PFCAs, supporting the claim that newly bought textiles contain more short-chain PFAAs than textiles produced several years ago.

The Greenpeace investigation of SHEIN products that tested selected swimwear items for PFAAs, had no detections. A few swimwear items were included in this project, including a post-consumer swimwear item which was the sample with the highest total PFAS detection of 98.29 ng/g (Appendix D.4). Also, a pair of swim shorts (Rec_20) for children was one of the samples with the highest total PFAS concentrations of 64.30 ng/g (Appendix D.3, A.1). The Greenpeace study had consecutively higher LODs than this project ranging from 5 to 21 ng/g whilst most of the LODs in this study were below 0.2 ng/ml (table 4.3). This study had higher sensitivity than the Greenpeace study, managing to show that both recycled and post-consumer swimwear items may contain PFAAs.

The study investigating if "green" assurances can indicate no PFAS in the products, detected

no PFAS in the targeted PFAS analysis for products without water- or stain-resistance. 4/14 of these products though had detections over the LOQ (10ppm) for the total fluorine screening. In that study, they decided not to test many of these non-functional samples due to low detection in the total F screening^[46]. Contradictory to that, this study has shown that most textiles without stain-or water-repellence marketing have at least one of the target PFAS present. Even 3 of the recycled samples that were labeled with the OEKO-TEX Standard 100 Ecolabel: REC_1, REC_25, and REC_34 (A.1), had at least one targeted PFAS detection. REC_1 and REC_34 had detections of two target PFAS and total PFAS concentrations of 2.71 ng/g and 0.91 ng/g respectively and, REC_25 had detections of 4 target PFAS and a total PFAS concentration of 5.54 ng/g. The label is supposed to ensure the customer that the article has been tested for harmful substances and that the product is harmless for human health^[94], but this is not entirely true since they only test for the selection of PFAS, and uses limit values instead of claiming do detection^[48]. This project can also confirm that green assurances do not always indicate the absence of PFAS.

The H&M and IKEA study on post-consumer cotton, polyester, and wool^[49] found that post-consumer polyester had the widest variety of substances detected, and PFAS was only detected in polyester samples. This study can confirm that post-consumer textile samples had overall higher total PFAS concentrations than the newly purchased samples (figure 4.1 and 4.2). But at least one PFAS was detected in nearly all samples, and the synthetic fabrics had substantially higher median total PFAS concentration than natural materials and mixed materials for short-chain PFCAs and “other PFAS” (Figure 4.4). This project showed the detection of all PFAS groups in post-consumer textiles of natural materials like cotton and wool as well, disproving the claim that these are typically PFAS-free and reliable sources of recyclable materials that can be used without putting PFAS back in the recycling loop. Exact detection values and method information has not been published for the study from H&M and IKEA, so possible reasons caused by the method that might have led to low detection rate (like high LODs) are unknown.

4.5 Comparison with regulatory limits

No samples exceeded the EU's POPs regulation limits for PFOA of 25 ng/g, but 3 samples exceeded the limits for PFOS at 0.1 ng/cm². These were all post-consumer samples: FX_4 (sports-sweater), FX_9 (socks) and FX_27 (socks) with PFOS concentrations of 0.125 ng/cm², 1.187 ng/cm² and 0.494 ng/cm², respectively. The regulation states that articles or semi-finished textiles should not be placed on the market if the amount of PFAS is equal to or higher than this limit in the material. The sports sweater was of synthetic materials, and would probably not undergo clothing-to-clothing recycling considering the lack of feasible recycling methods for synthetic textiles, but it may have been subject to reselling in thrift shops or donated to people in need, keeping an item of illegal PFOS limits in use. It was not possible to know exactly what kind of material the socks were made of, but they were considered "wool-like". They could potentially be subject to mechanical recycling, and high amounts of PFOS would have stayed in the new recycled products. Even though most samples did not exceed these limits, the accumulation of PFAS chemicals that it has been revealed that they contain might occur if they are subject to textile recycling.

5 Implications, recommendations, and conclusions

5.1 Implications and recommendations for a cleaner circular economy

The results from this study have shown the presence of PFAS in non-functional recycled textiles and rejected post-consumer textiles. The chosen method showed good method performance characteristics and even though levels are considered low the research showed the ubiquitous presence of PFAS in these types of textiles. The sample batch was chosen to give an overview of common types of textiles a regular consumer usually buys and discards to a textile collecting station. Most of the textiles were attire that is worn close to the body, exposing the wearer to hazardous chemicals attached to fibers that could shed and reach the mouth or be absorbed dermally^[58]. These types of textiles will most likely go through numerous laundering cycles during the use stage, the dominant life cycle stage for emission of PFAS from textiles^[27]. Release of PFAS in water used to wash the textiles before sample treatment was detected, implying washing of non-functional textiles contributes to the overall emission of PFAS to the environment. The presence of PFAS in the water is most likely from the residue of the packaging they were stored and shipped in for the recycled samples that are more easily washable and dirt from the use and sorting of the post-consumer samples. To remove PFAS residue from the packaging of newly purchased textiles, they should be washed before use (with PFAS-free detergent) to remove the more easily washable substances to decrease PFAS exposure when wearing new clothes to minimize exposure, even though they will be released to waste-water treatment with insufficient technology to remove them.

Post-consumer textiles are materials with great potential of being utilized in a new circular textile economy where recycling operates at scale. Regarding the concern of hazardous chemicals present in the materials following along during circulation, this study has confirmed that PFAS present in post-consumer textiles will be a problem for creating toxic-free cycles to combat the huge waste problem caused by high demands of new textiles from consumers pushed by fast-and ultra-fast fashion. It is already shown that the textiles industry is a major user and polluter of hazardous chemicals, being a top industry considering PFAS use^[4]. Because of this, trace amounts of these chemicals in non-functional textiles where PFAS is not intentionally added are not a surprise. Due to the extreme stability and persistence of PFAS, they are not removed from the fibers easily. Evidence of accumulation of chemicals in other materials^{[9][10][80]} is a real concern for the vision of accelerating textile recycling in the future. PFAS were detected in all types of materials (natural, synthetic, and mixed), so recyclers can not rely on a specific material type to be PFAS-free for use as secondary materials. Even though mechanical recycling is most easily done using natural fibers, recycling synthetic fibers is an option as well, and is desired due to the high yield of synthetic fibers being produced. Since textiles are a source for particles in airborne dust, concerns of workers' exposure in future larger-scale textile recycling stations is a concern, as textile workers are exposed to textile process dust from particularly wool and cotton^[63] and accumulation of PFAS in textile fibers could increase the risk of these workers' PFAS exposure.

Previous studies showing accumulation of hazardous chemicals in recycled plastics, metals, and paper would lead to the assumption that recycled textiles would contain more PFAS than post-consumer textiles. This study showed the contradictory; post-consumer textiles had overall higher concentrations of PFAS. The newer textiles purchased in this study made of recycled materials, was for the most part not made from post-consumer textiles, but rather excess cotton or wool, “scraps” gathered from production facilities, or old plastic products transformed into synthetic fibers.

To achieve a safe circular economy that uses textiles already produced rather than extracting raw resources, products need to be durable and safe for reuse, remanufacturing, and recycling. The technology for removing contaminants during the recycling process is not mature, and information about chemical substances present in textiles is often not disclosed. Sorting facilities for discarded post-consumer textiles have little to no information regarding the items they receive. Increased transparency across the industry needs to happen along with the implementation of better sorting so that post-consumer textiles can be better utilized in a toxic-free circular economy.

The best and most effective measure to eliminate hazardous substances is to not add them at all through improved design that will not cause damage to human and ecological health. Even if a full stop of PFAS use is implemented, it could take decades before chemical content in recycled products could be considered insignificant^[80]. A full ban on PFAS should happen as soon as possible. A no-use approach in every stage of textile production, not just during finishing processes, but also for use as processing aids for equipment lubrication, washing, and dyeing of textiles is the most effective way of tackling the problem. Therefore, a full ban on PFAS use and manufacture is necessary to combat this challenge. The ongoing deliberation of the ECHA restriction proposal of 10 000 PFAS should consider not only the concerns for levels already existing in the environment that will continue to rise if a phase-out is not happening through restriction but also see the risks of these chemicals recirculating in the EU’s own vision of accelerating reuse and recycling. And most importantly the proposal should be accepted.

5.2 Final conclusions

PFAS concentrations in two types of non-functional textiles have been analyzed using UPLC-QqQ-ESI-MS/MS: recycled textiles made fully or partly from recycled fibers and rejected post-consumer textiles collected from Fretex. Nearly all (96%) samples had at least one detection of a target PFAS, and PFOS was the most frequently detected PFAS. The detected concentration ranges were comparable to previous studies analyzing ionic PFAS in non-functional textiles and similar to the lower ranges of previous studies analyzing ionic PFAS in functional textiles.

The post-consumer textiles had consecutively higher total PFAS concentrations than the recycled samples along with higher detection frequencies of all groups of PFAS except short-chain PFCAs. The contributions of different PFAS types in recycled textiles followed the order PFCAs > other PFASs > long-chain PFCAs > long-chain PFSAs > short-chain PFSAs whilst the contributions of different PFAS types in post-consumer textiles followed the order long-chain PFSAs > short-

chain PFCAs > other PFAS > long-chain PFCAs > short-chain PFASs. The domination of long-chain PFASs in post-consumer textiles was mostly due to notably high detected concentrations levels of PFDoDS. These findings supports the evidence of the shift in the textile industry in recent years from the use of long-chain PFAS to short-chained analogs since the post-consumer textiles were most likely produced several years ago, which has been demonstrated in previous studies focusing on functional textiles.

Synthetic materials had substantially higher median values of short-chain PFCAs and “other PFAS” than natural or mixed materials. Big differences between material types across all samples were not seen for other types of PFAS. The market study initiated by H&M and IKEA investigating chemical content in post-consumer textiles found that only polyester samples contained PFAS, but this research has shown the presence of natural and mixed materials in addition to polyester in both post-consumer and recycled non-functional textiles. In the textiles of natural material, recycled textiles had higher median values than the post-consumer samples, but these differences are very small, and overall, post-consumer textiles of natural material contained a higher amount of total PFAS.

PFAS was also detected in water used to wash the textile samples in the sample pre-treatment. All water samples had detections of at least one target compound, and diSAMPAP was detected in all water samples over the LOQ, showing that wash off of PFAS from non-functional textiles could contribute to the emission of PFAS to the environment in the use-phase of textiles like it has been shown in functional textiles.

The presence of PFAS in non-functional textiles poses threats to consumers and is a hinder to achieving clean material cycles under the ambitions of the EU Green Deal. PFAS in textiles worn close to the body could expose the wearer through inhalation or dermal absorption and the presence of persistent chemicals in textiles is a chemical roadblock to achieving a non-toxic circular economy. Technology for removing contamination in secondary resources is not mature, and the focus should be aimed on eliminating hazardous chemicals in the design phase. Strict regulations need to be in place since the industry will not stop the use otherwise. The recent proposal from ECHA to ban the use of over 10 000 PFAS could be a major step in achieving a new circular textile economy free of PFAS.

References

- [1] J. Glüge, M. Scheringer, I. T. Cousins, J. C. DeWitt, G. Goldenman, D. Herzke, R. Lohmann, C. A. Ng, X. Trier, and Z. Wang, “An overview of the uses of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS),” *Environmental science–processes & impacts*, vol. 22, no. 12, pp. 2345–2373, 2020.
- [2] J. C. DeWitt, “Toxicological effects of perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances,” 2015.
- [3] D. Muir, R. Bossi, P. Carlsson, M. Evans, A. De Silva, C. Halsall, C. Rauert, D. Herzke, H. Hung, R. Letcher, F. Rigét, and A. Roos, “Levels and trends of poly- and perfluoroalkyl substances in the arctic environment - An update,” *Emerging Contaminants*, vol. 5, pp. 240–271, 2019.
- [4] ECHA. European Chemicals Agency, “Annex xv restriction report. proposal for a restriction,” 2023. <https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/f605d4b5-7c17-7414-8823-b49b9fd43aea>.
- [5] P. J. Hill, M. Taylor, P. Goswami, and R. S. Blackburn, “Substitution of pfas chemistry in outdoor apparel and the impact on repellency performance,” *Chemosphere (Oxford)*, vol. 181, pp. 500–507, 2017.
- [6] *Polyfluorinated Chemicals and Transformation Products*, vol. 17 of *The Handbook of Environmental Chemistry*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [7] I. T. Cousins, J. H. Johansson, M. E. Salter, B. Sha, and M. Scheringer, “Outside the safe operating space of a new planetary boundary for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS),” *Environmental science technology*, vol. 56, no. 16, pp. 11172–11179, 2022.
- [8] Ellen McArthur Foundation, “A new textiles economy: Redesigning fashion’s future,” tech. rep., 2017, <http://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/publications>.
- [9] ChemSec, “What goes around: Enabling the circular economy by removing chemical roadblocks,” tech. rep., 2021. <https://chemsec.org/publication/chemicals-business-circular-economy/what-goes-around/>.
- [10] N. Johansson, *The policy conflict between circularity and toxicity: Problems, perspectives and strategies*. TRITA-ABE-RPT, 2022.
- [11] R. C. Buck, J. Franklin, U. Berger, J. M. Conder, I. T. Cousins, P. de Voogt, A. A. Jensen, K. Kannan, S. A. Mabury, and S. P. van Leeuwen, “Perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances in the environment: Terminology, classification, and origins,” *Integrated environmental assessment and management*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 513–541, 2011.
- [12] N. National Center For Biotechnology Information, “Pubchem classification browser,” 2023. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/classification/#hid=120> (Accessed: 21.05.23).
- [13] ITRC, “Naming conventions for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (pfas),” tech. rep., 2022.

- https://pfas-1.itrcweb.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/NamingConventions_PFAS_Fact-Sheet_083122_508.pdf.
- [14] Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP), “Amap assessment 2016: Chemicals of emerging arctic concern,” tech. rep., 2017.
- [15] P. Kirsch, “Modern fluoroorganic chemistry : synthesis, reactivity, applications,” 2013.
- [16] D. M. Lemal, “Perspective on fluorocarbon chemistry,” vol. 69, no. 1, pp. 1–11, 2004.
- [17] E. Kissa, *Fluorinated Surfactants and Repellents, Second Edition*,. Surfactant Science, Taylor & Francis, 2001.
- [18] N. L. Stock, V. I. Furdui, D. C. G. Muir, and S. A. Mabury, “Perfluoroalkyl contaminants in the canadian Arctic: Evidence of Atmospheric Transport and Local Contamination,” *Environmental science & technology*, vol. 41, no. 10, pp. 3529–3536, 2007.
- [19] Y. Manojkumar, S. Pilli, P. V. Rao, and R. D. Tyagi, “Sources, occurrence and toxic effects of emerging per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS),” *Neurotoxicology and teratology*, vol. 97, pp. 107174–107174, 2023.
- [20] S. Brendel, E. Fetter, C. Staude, L. Vierke, and A. Biegel-Engler, “Short-chain perfluoroalkyl acids: environmental concerns and a regulatory strategy under reach,” *Environmental sciences Europe*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 9–9, 2018.
- [21] EPA, “What are PFAS?.” <https://www.epa.ie/our-services/monitoring--assessment/waste/chemicals/pfas/>, 2023. (Accessed: 2023-03-23).
- [22] ChemSec, “The teflon chemical PTFE is often touted as a safe cousin of toxic pfas. but is it really?.” <https://chemsec.org/the-teflon-chemical-ptfe-is-often-touted-as-a-safe-cousin-of-toxic-pfas-but-is-it-real> (Accessed: 17.04.23).
- [23] N. E. Clough and I. W. L. Gore & Associated, “Innovations in eptfe fiber technology: New capabilities, new applications, new opportunities.” https://www.gore.co.jp/sites/default/files/2016-04/ePTFE_INNOVATIONS_WHITE_PAPER.pdf.
- [24] B. J. Spillum, “Polymerfeber.” <https://sml.snl.no/polymerfeber> (Accessed: 17.04.23).
- [25] R. A. Horrocks and S. C. Anand, *Handbook of Technical Textiles, Volume 1 - Technical Textile Processes (2nd Edition)*. Elsevier, 2016.
- [26] Lenzing Group, “Stand up for future generations,” p. 47, 2020. https://www.lenzing.com/type=88245&tx_filedownloads_file%5bfileName%5d=fileadmin/content/PDF/07_Finzen/Geschaeftsberichte/EN/GB_2020_EN.pdf,.
- [27] R. Witing, L. Nicol, I. Keyte, J. KreiBig, M. Crookes, W. Gebbink, A. Potrykus, and M. Schopel, “The use of PFAS and fluorine-free alternatives in textiles, upholstery, carpets, leather and apparel,” tech. rep., 2020. https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13641/pfas_in_textiles_final_report_en.pdf/0a3b1c60-3427-5327-4a19-4d98ee06f041.

- [28] L. Segedie, “Non-toxic activewear guide: PFAS “forever chemicals” in workout leggings & yoga pants,” 2022. <https://www.mamavation.com/product-investigations/non-toxic-activewear-guide-pfas-workout-leggings-yoga-pants.html>.
- [29] J. Roth, B. Zerger, and S. R. Damien De Geeter, Jorge Gómez Benavides, “Best available techniques (bat) reference document for the textiles industry,” tech. rep., OECD, 2023. Luxembourg. JRC 131874 <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ad7cea9f-97ab-11ed-b508-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>.
- [30] The European Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control Bureau (EIPPCB), “Best available techniques (BAT) reference document for the textiles industry,” tech. rep., 2023. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2760/355887>.
- [31] UNEP, “Guidance for the inventory of perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS) and related chemicals listed under the stockholm convention on persistent organic pollutants,” tech. rep., 2017. UNEP/POPS/COP.7/INF/26.
- [32] Greenpeace, “Taking the shine off shein: A business model based on hazardous chemicals and environmental destruction,” tech. rep., 2022. https://www.greenpeace.de/publikationen/S04261_Konsumwende_StudieEN_Mehr%20Schein_v9.pdf.
- [33] J. Cowley, S. Matteis, and C. Agro, “Experts warn of high levels of chemicals in clothes by some fast-fashion retailers,” 2021. <https://www.cbc.ca/news/business/marketplace-fast-fashion-chemicals-1.6193385> (Accessed: 11.04.23).
- [34] C. Xia, M. L. Diamond, G. F. Peaslee, H. Peng, A. Blum, Z. Wang, A. Shalin, H. D. Whitehead, M. Green, H. Schwartz-Narbonne, D. Yang, and M. Venier, “Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in north american school uniforms,” *Environmental science technology*, vol. 56, no. 19, pp. 13845–13857, 2022.
- [35] C. Gremmel, T. Frömel, and T. P. Knepper, “Systematic determination of perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) in outdoor jackets,” *Chemosphere (Oxford)*, vol. 160, pp. 173–180, 2016.
- [36] U. Berge and D. Herzke, “Per-and polyfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS) extracted from textile samples,” *Organohalogen Compounds*, vol. 68, no. 68, pp. 2023–2026, 2006.
- [37] G. Zheng and A. Salamova, “Are melamine and its derivatives the alternatives for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substance (PFAS) fabric treatments in infant clothes?,” *Environmental science & technology*, vol. 54, no. 16, pp. 10207–10216, 2020.
- [38] X. Liu, Z. Guo, K. A. Krebs, R. H. Pope, and N. F. Roache, “Concentrations and trends of perfluorinated chemicals in potential indoor sources from 2007 through 2011 in the us,” *Chemosphere (Oxford)*, vol. 98, pp. 51–57, 2014.
- [39] P. Supreeyasunthorn, S. K. Boontanon, and N. Boontanon, “Perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) and perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) contamination from textiles,” vol. 51, no. 6, pp. 472–477, 2016.

- [40] I. van der Veen, A.-C. Hanning, A. Stare, P. E. Leonards, J. de Boer, and J. M. Weiss, “The effect of weathering on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) from durable water repellent (dwr) clothing,” *Chemosphere (Oxford)*, vol. 249, pp. 126100–126100, 2020.
- [41] S. Schellenberger, I. Liagkouridis, R. Awad, S. Khan, M. Plassmann, G. Peters, J. P. Ben-skin, and I. T. Cousins, “An outdoor aging study to investigate the release of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) from functional textiles,” *Environmental science & technology*, vol. 56, no. 6, pp. 3471–3479, 2022.
- [42] The Danish Environmental Protection Agency, “Polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) in tex-tiles for children,” tech. rep., 2015. <https://www2.mst.dk/Udgiv/publications/2022/11/978-87-7038-458-2.pdf>.
- [43] A. E. Robel, K. Marshall, M. Dickinson, D. Lunderberg, C. Butt, G. Peaslee, H. M. Sta-pleton, and J. A. Field, “Closing the mass balance on fluorine on papers and textiles,” *Environmental science & technology*, vol. 51, no. 16, pp. 9022–9032, 2017.
- [44] Z. Guo, X. Liu, and K. A. Krebs, “Perfluorocarboxylic acid content in 116 articles of com-merce,” tech. rep., 2009. EPA/600/R-09/033.
- [45] H. Zhu and K. Kannan, “Total oxidizable precursor assay in the determination of perflu-oroalkyl acids in textiles collected from the united states,” *Environmental pollution (1987)*, vol. 265, pp. 114940–114940, 2020.
- [46] K. M. Rodgers, C. H. Swartz, J. Occhialini, P. Bassignani, M. McCurdy, and L. A. Schaidler, “How well do product labels indicate the presence of pfas in consumer items used by children and adolescents?,” *Environmental science & technology*, vol. 56, no. 10, pp. 6294–6304, 2022.
- [47] J. Choy, “My menstrual underwear has toxic chemicals in it,” 2020. <https://www.sierraclub.org/sierra/ask-ms-green/my-menstrual-underwear-has-toxic-chemicals-it>.
- [48] L. Segedie, “Report: 65% of period underwear tested likely contami-nated with PFAS chemicals,” 2021. <https://www.mamavation.com/health/period-underwear-contaminated-pfas-chemicals.html>.
- [49] H&M group, “Large scale study from H&M group and IKEA shows potential to transform the way we use recycled textiles.” <https://hmgroup.com/news/large-scale-study-from-hm-group-and-ikea-shows-potential-to-transform-the-way-we-use-r> 2021. (Accessed: 25.04.23).
- [50] Apparel and Footwear International RSL Management (AFIRM) Group, “Restricted sub-stances list.” <https://afirm-group.com/afirm-rsl/>, 2023.
- [51] H&M group, Inter IKEA Group, and ChemSec, “Collaborative study on chemicals in recy-cled textiles,” 2021. Presentation from webinar.
- [52] Bluesign Technologies, “Selecting dyes and chemicals to minimise environmental impacts

- AFIRM RSL seminar presentation,” 2007. <https://afirm-group.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Bluesign-Presentation-1.pdf>.
- [53] O. Yallop, “Citarum, the most polluted river in the world?.” *The Telegraph*, April 2014. <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/earth/environment/10761077/Citarum-the-most-polluted-river-in-the-world.html> (Accessed: 24.03.23).
- [54] Greenpeace, “Destination zero: Seven years of detoxing the clothing industry,” tech. rep., 2018. https://www.greenpeace.org/static/planet4-international-stateless/2018/07/destination_zero_report_july_2018.pdf.
- [55] European Environment Agency, “Fluorinated polymers in a low carbon, circular and toxic-free economy,” tech. rep., 2021. Eionet Report - ETC/WMGE 2021/9 <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-wmge/products/etc-wmge-reports/fluorinated-polymers-in-a-low-carbon-circular-and-toxic-free-economy>.
- [56] KEMI, “Chemicals in textiles: Risks to human health and the environment,” tech. rep., 2014. <https://www.kemi.se/en/publications/reports/2014/report-6-14-chemicals-in-textiles>.
- [57] P. De Voogt and D. M. Whitacre, “Biodegradation of fluorinated alkyl substances,” in *Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology Volume 208*, vol. 208 of *Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology*, pp. 161–177, United States: Springer New York, 2010.
- [58] D. Licina, G. C. Morrison, G. Bekö, C. J. Weschler, and W. W. Nazaroff, “Clothing-mediated exposures to chemicals and particles,” *Environmental science & technology*, vol. 53, no. 10, pp. 5559–5575, 2019.
- [59] M. A.-E. Abdallah and S. Harrad, “Dermal contact with furniture fabrics is a significant pathway of human exposure to brominated flame retardants,” *Environment international*, vol. 118, pp. 26–33, 2018.
- [60] G. Pawar, M. A.-E. Abdallah, E. V. De Sáa, and S. Harrad, “Dermal bioaccessibility of flame retardants from indoor dust and the influence of topically applied cosmetics,” *Journal of exposure science & environmental epidemiology*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 100–105, 2017.
- [61] O. Ragnarsdóttir, M. A.-E. Abdallah, and S. Harrad, “Dermal uptake: An important pathway of human exposure to perfluoroalkyl substances?,” *Environmental pollution (1987)*, vol. 307, pp. 119478–119478, 2022.
- [62] U. Eriksson and A. Kärman, “World-wide indoor exposure to polyfluoroalkyl phosphate esters (PAPs) and other PFASs in household dust,” *Environmental science & technology*, vol. 49, no. 24, pp. 14503–14511, 2015.
- [63] Health and Safety Executive, (HSE), “Dust. why dust is a problem,” 2023. <https://www.hse.gov.uk/textiles/dust.htm> (Accessed: 25.05.23).
- [64] F. Heydebreck, J. Tang, Z. Xie, and R. Ebinghaus, “Emissions of per- and polyfluoroalkyl

- substances in a textile manufacturing plant in china and their relevance for workers' exposure," *Environmental science & technology*, vol. 50, no. 19, pp. 10386–10396, 2016.
- [65] United Nations, "The new POPs under the stockholm convention." <http://chm.pops.int/TheConvention/ThePOPs/TheNewPOPs/tabid/2511/Default.aspx>. (Accessed : 27.03.23).
- [66] ECHA, "Understanding reach." <https://echa.europa.eu/regulations/reach/understanding-reach> (Accessed: 12.04.23).
- [67] ECHA, "Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS)." <https://echa.europa.eu/hot-topics/perfluoroalkyl-chemicals-pfas> (Accessed: 12.04.23).
- [68] European Union, "Regulation (eu) 2019/1021 of the european parliament and of the council of 20 june 2019 on persistent organic pollutants," 2019. Official Journal of the European Union, L 169/45.
- [69] Regjeringen, "Green deal." <https://www.regjeringen.no/no/sub/eos-notatbasen/notatene/2020/feb/green-deal/id2689681/>, 2020. (Accessed: 24.03.23).
- [70] European Commission, "A european green deal." https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en, 2023. (Accessed: 24.03.23).
- [71] European Commission, "Zero pollution action plan." https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/zero-pollution-action-plan_en.
- [72] European Commission, "Chemicals strategy." https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/chemicals-strategy_en, 2023. (Accessed: 24.03.23).
- [73] European Commission, "A new circular economy plan. for a cleaner and more competitive europe," tech. rep., 2020. Communication from the European Commission, COM(2020) 98 final <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1583933814386&uri=COM:2020:98:FIN>.
- [74] European Commission, "Strategy for textiles." https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/industry/sustainability/strategy-textiles_en (Accessed: 13.04.2023).
- [75] European Commission, "Communication from the commission to the european parliament, the council, the european economic and social committee and the committee of the regions." <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2020%3A667%3AFIN>, 2020.
- [76] European Commission, "EU strategy for sustainable and circular textiles." https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/textiles-strategy_en (Accessed: 13.04.2023).
- [77] Greenpeace, "Self regulation: a fashion fairytale," tech. rep., 2021. <https://www.greenpeace.org/international/publication/50922/self-regulation-fashion-supply-chain-fairytale/>.
- [78] M. Kotthoff, J. Müller, H. Jürling, M. Schlummer, and D. Fiedler, "Perfluoroalkyl and

- polyfluoroalkyl substances in consumer products,” *Environmental science and pollution research international*, vol. 22, no. 19, pp. 14546–14559, 2015.
- [79] E. Parliament, “Circular economy: definition, importance and benefits.” <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/headlines/economy/20151201ST005603/circular-economy-definition-importance-and-benefits> (Accessed: 08.05.23).
- [80] K. Pivnenko, D. Laner, and T. F. Astrup, “Material cycles and chemicals: Dynamic material flow analysis of contaminants in paper recycling,” *Environmental science & technology*, vol. 50, no. 22, pp. 12302–12311, 2016.
- [81] J. Lee, A. B. Pedersen, and M. Thomsen, “The influence of resource strategies on childhood phthalate exposure—the role of REACH in a zero waste society,” *Environment international*, vol. 73, pp. 312–322, 2014.
- [82] E. Lundanes, “Chromatography : basic principles, sample preparations and related methods,” 2014.
- [83] D. A. Skoog, “Fundamentals of analytical chemistry,” 2022.
- [84] S. C. Mandal, V. Mandal, and A. K. Das, “Classification of extraction methods,” in *Essentials of Botanical Extraction*, United States: Elsevier Science & Technology, 2015.
- [85] R. Kellner, J.-M. Mermet, M. Otto, M. Valcárcel, and H. M. Widmer, “Analytical chemistry : a modern approach to analytical science,” 2004.
- [86] E. Lundanes, “Chromatography: basic principles, sample preparations and related methods,” 2014.
- [87] R. E. Ardrey, “Liquid chromatography - mass spectrometry : an introduction,” 2003.
- [88] A. Shrivastava, V. B. Gupta, *et al.*, “Methods for the determination of limit of detection and limit of quantitation of the analytical methods,” *Chron. Young Sci*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 21–25, 2011.
- [89] H. Trufelli, P. Palma, G. Famigliani, and A. Cappiello, “An overview of matrix effects in liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry,” *Mass spectrometry reviews*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 491–509, 2011.
- [90] D. Thakur, N. P. Dubey, and R. Singh, “A review on spike and recovery method in analytical method development and validation,” *Critical reviews in analytical chemistry*, vol. ahead-of-print, no. ahead-of-print, pp. 1–19, 2022.
- [91] A. L. B. Sin, “Perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances in consumer products, fast food packaging, waste electrical and electronic equipment, and end-of-life vehicle residual fluff in a circular economy,” 2020. Master Thesis. Unpublished.
- [92] O. S. Arvaniti, A. G. Asimakopoulos, M. E. Dasenaki, E. I. Ventouri, A. S. Stasinakis, and N. S. Thomaidis, “Simultaneous determination of eighteen perfluorinated compounds in dissolved and particulate phases of wastewater, and in sewage sludge by liquid

- chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry,” *Analytical Methods*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 1341–1349, 2014.
- [93] I. van der Veen, S. Schellenberger, A.-C. Hanning, A. Stare, J. de Boer, J. M. Weiss, and P. E. G. Leonards, “Fate of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances from durable water-repellent clothing during use,” *Environmental science & technology*, vol. 56, no. 9, pp. 5886–5897, 2022.
- [94] OEKO-TEX, “Oeko-tex® standard 100,” 2023. <https://www.oeko-tex.com/en/our-standards/oeko-tex-standard-100> (Accessed: 15.05.23).

A Sample information

Table A.1: Sample information of all samples, recycled and post-consumer (labelled REC and FX). Sample ID, type of item, if made for adults/children/babies, type of material, country of origin and Ecolabel information

Sample ID	Item	Children/ Adult/ Baby	Material	Made in	Ecolabel
Recycled textiles					
REC_1	T-shirt	Adult	50% recycled open end cotton, 50% organic raw open end cotton		GOTS, GRS, PETA, OEKO-TEX Standard 100
REC_2	Bikini top	Adult	87 % recycled polyester, 13% elastan	Europe	GOTS, GRA
REC_3	Bikini bottom	Adult	78% recycled nylon, 22% elastan Lining: 83% recycled nylon, 17% elastan		GOTS
REC_4	Bikini Bottom	Adult	87% recycled polyester, 13% elastan	Spain	
REC_5	Face Mask	Adult	65% recycled polyester and 35% elastane		
REC_6	Face Mask	Children	100% Recycled Polyester		
REC_7	Bra	Adult	92% Recycled Polyamide, 8% Elastane		
REC_8	Beanie	Children	70% recycled wool, 25% polyamide, 5% other fibres		
REC_9	Socks	Children	43% polyamide (13% recycled) 25% recycled wool, 26% recycled rayon, 5% recycled cashmere		
REC_10	Socks	Adult	51% Recycled Cotton, 18% Recycled Repreve® Polyester 25% Recycled Polyester 4% Recycled Polyamide 2% Recycled Elastane		
REC_11	Underwear	Adult	83% recycled polyamid, 17% elastane		
REC_12	Gloves (innermaterial)	Children			
REC_13	Gloves (outer material 1)	Children	50% polyamide, 50% polyurethane		BIONIC-FINISH ECO
REC_14	Gloves (outer material 2)	Children			BIONIC-FINISH ECO
REC_15	Socks	Adult	51% Recycled Cotton, 25% , Recycled Polyester, 4% Recycled Polyamide, 2% Recycled Elastane		
REC_16	Gloves	Baby	50% recycled polyester, 49% Acrylic, 1% Elastan		
REC_17	Stockings	Adult	90% recycled polyamid, 10% elastan		
REC_18	Socks	Children	75% Recycled polyester, 23% polyester, 2% Elastane		
REC_19	Swimsuit	Children	84% Recycled Polyester, 16% Elastane		
REC_20	Swimshorts	Children	100% Recycled polyester		
REC_21	Filling		85% recycled cotton, 15% other fibres		
REC_22	Ribbon		90% recycle cotton, 10% other recycled fibers		
REC_23	Ribbon		80% recycled cotton, 20% other recycled fibers		
REC_24	Ribbon		85% recycled cotton, 15% other fibres		
REC_25	yarn		100% recycled cotton		OEKO-TEX Standard 100
REC_26	yarn		100% recycled cotton		
REC_27	ribbon		100% recycled cotton		
REC_28	yarn		100% recycled cotton		
REC_29	ribbon		100% recycled cotton	Turkey	
REC_30	yarn		100% recycled fibres (mainly cotton)		
REC_31	yarn		80% recycled cotton, 20% other recycled fibers		
REC_32	yarn		95% recycled cotton, 5% other fibers		
REC_33	yarn		52% recycled cotton, 48% recycled polyester	Italy	
REC_34	yarn		100% recycled cotton	Turkey	OEKO-TEX Standard 100
REC_35	yarn		80% recycled cotton, 15% cotton, 5 % other fibers		
REC_36	yarn		95% recycled cotton, 5% other fibers		
REC_37	Thread		100% recycled polyester		
Fretex textiles					
FX_1	Body	Baby	100% cotton	Bangladesh	
FX_2	T-shirt	Adult	100% cotton	Bangladesh	
FX_3	Tights	Adult	81% polyamide, 19% elastan	Italy	
FX_4	Sports-sweater	Adult	62% polyamide, 38% polyester		
FX_5	Stockings	Adult	70% cotton, 25% polyester, 5% elastan		
FX_6	Socks	Adult	wool-like		
FX_7	Socks	Adult	cooton-like		
FX_8	Socks	Adult	probably mixed		
FX_9	Socks	Adult	wool-like		
FX_10	Sports T-shirt	Adult	100% polyester	Cambodia	
FX_11	Stockings	Adult	wool-ish		
FX_12	Socks	Adult	cotton-like		
FX_13	Socks	Children	cotton-like		
FX_14	socks	Adult	probably mixed		
FX_15	socks	Adult	cotton-like		
FX_16	Pants	Children	62% polyester, 34% viscose, 4% elastane	Turkey	
FX_17	T-shirt	Adult	100% cotton	China	
FX_18	T-shirt	Adult	100% cotton	India	
FX_19	Sports T- shirt	Adult	100% polyester	Estonia	
FX_20	Sports T- shirt	Adult	92% polyester, 8% spandex		
FX_21	Sports- Sweater	Adult	89% polyester, 11% elastan	Myanmar	
FX_22	Shorts	Children	98% cotton, 2% elastane		
FX_23	Bralette	Adult	96% nylon, 4% spandex		
FX_24	Bikini bottom	Adult	synthetic		
FX_25	Pants	Adult	100% cotton	Bangladesh	
FX_26	T-shirt	Adult	100% cotton	Honduras	
FX_27	Socks	Adult	wool-like		
FX_28	T-shirt	Adult	100% cotton		
FX_29	T-shirt	Children	100% cotton	Bangladesh	
FX_30	Stockings	Children	70% bomull, 25% polyester		

B Concentrations in water samples

Table B.1: Concentrations in ng/ml for 10 water samples analyzed after the third wash. Target PFAS without any detections are excluded.

Compound	REC_2	REC_5	REC_11	REC_1	FX_4	FX_7	FX_14	FX_15	FX_20	FX_30
PFPeA	<LOQ	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	0.069	n.d	n.d
4:2 FTS	n.d	<LOQ	n.d	n.d	n.d	<LOQ	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
7H-PFHpA	n.d	n.d	n.d	0.028	n.d	n.d	0.034	0.159	n.d	n.d
6:2 FTS	0.004	0.036	0.005	<LOQ	0.005	<LOQ	0.004	n.d	n.d	n.d
PFOS	n.d	n.d	<LOQ	n.d	n.d	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.017	n.d	<LOQ
MeFOSA	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	<LOQ	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
EtFOSA	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	<LOQ	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	<LOQ
EtFOSAA	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	0.002	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	<LOQ
MeFOSAA	n.d	0.003	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
diSAMPAP	0.020	0.076	0.009	0.015	0.003	0.008	0.007	0.006	0.029	0.006
PFBS	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	0.009	n.d
PFPeS	n.d	n.d	0.011	n.d	n.d	<LOQ	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d
PFECHS	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	0.008	n.d
PFDS	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	0.006	n.d	0.002	n.d	0.064	0.007
PFDoDS	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	0.038	n.d	0.074	n.d	0.054

C Quality control parameters

Table C.1: Quality control parameters for 41 target compounds for the two methods tested: Protocol 1 (P1) and Protocol 2 (P2). Absolute recoveries (AR), Relative recoveries (RR), Matrix effects (ME), and RSD values for each respective parameter

Compound	P1		P2		P1		P2		P1		P2	
	AR (%)	RSD	AR (%)	RSD	RR (%)	RSD	RR (%)	RSD	ME (%)	RSD	ME (%)	RSD
DecaS	87	0.31	53	0.78	100	0.20	61	0.62	58	0.03	83	0.07
GenX	102	0.12	67	0.32	107	0.03	73	0.00	-32	0.14	-10	0.07
PFPeA	95	0.27	57	0.31	99	0.18	59	0.03	23	0.10	33	0.23
PFHxA	88	0.46	55	0.50	90	0.33	61	0.05	-65	0.26	-17	0.42
4:2 FTS	89	0.21	54	0.53	93	0.12	59	0.13	-30	0.12	17	0.22
7H-PFHpA	93	0.31	80	0.09	96	0.19	85	0.01	-22	0.11	9	0.07
NaDONA	96	0.16	75	0.31	101	0.03	81	0.32	-33	0.09	-30	0.07
PFOA	86	0.05	75	0.25	102	0.13	92	0.22	-40	0.07	-33	0.02
6:2 FTS	101	0.11	98	0.09	107	0.08	107	0.01	18	0.16	46	0.22
PFHpS	86	0.14	86	0.11	101	0.03	108	0.35	-26	0.04	-24	0.08
PFNA	94	0.17	68	0.30	107	0.02	80	1.81	-47	0.00	-44	0.04
P37DMOA	93	0.12	83	0.14	108	0.05	97	0.80	-13	0.04	-6	0.04
PFOSA	122	0.37	112	0.31	137	0.24	130	2.54	-81	0.09	-67	0.09
PFOS	89	0.13	79	0.17	103	0.08	92	0.36	-21	0.02	-18	0.03
MeFOSA	115	0.58	67	0.27	127	0.52	78	0.71	-75	0.11	-41	0.04
PFDA	112	0.13	89	0.36	131	0.21	103	0.29	-40	0.01	-45	0.12
EtFOSA	165	0.73	66	0.36	180	0.70	76	1.74	-86	0.27	-36	0.00
EtFOSAA	171	0.73	64	0.34	187	0.71	74	1.56	-84	0.26	-19	0.02
8:2 FTS	108	0.09	111	0.25	126	0.09	129	1.04	25	0.17	82	0.18
9Cl-PF3ONS	89	0.17	84	0.12	102	0.06	99	0.95	-9	0.04	3	0.01
FOSAA	76	0.26	81	0.12	86	0.12	96	1.99	-25	0.01	8	0.07
PFUnA	119	0.20	94	0.47	136	0.05	109	3.38	-71	0.02	-55	0.19
MeFOSAA	108	0.24	111	0.39	123	0.11	131	3.67	-57	0.05	-40	0.01
EtFOSE	132	0.70	90	0.24	144	0.65	104	0.03	-77	0.20	-41	0.03
PFDoDA	120	0.43	111	0.31	134	0.27	129	2.10	-84	0.15	-74	0.20
MeFOSE	125	0.45	90	0.23	139	0.35	104	0.02	-51	0.10	-30	0.01
10:2 FTS	110	0.29	75	0.14	125	0.15	89	0.53	-40	0.02	8	0.25
PFTriDA	130	0.69	89	0.06	142	0.61	106	0.26	-79	0.05	-69	0.35
diSAMPAP	324	0.89	143	0.86	360	0.94	161	5.36	-90	0.10	-37	0.07
PFTDA	176	0.82	63	0.59	193	0.84	71	1.23	-87	0.19	-72	0.12
PFHxDA	264	0.99	31	1.20	296	1.04	35	0.84	-95	0.04	-43	0.04
PFBA	125	0.38	-	1.73	131	0.42	-	0.01	595	0.46	-100	-
PFBS	83	0.23	82	0.11	86	0.12	87	0.09	-24	0.02	-4	0.03
PFPeS	83	0.24	82	0.12	86	0.12	88	0.05	-31	0.02	-16	0.09
PFHpA	98	0.16	69	0.41	103	0.04	72	0.02	-49	0.08	-45	0.05
PFHxS	87	0.18	85	0.17	91	0.08	91	0.06	-27	0.02	-30	0.03
PFECHS	83	0.19	88	0.08	87	0.09	94	0.38	-12	0.06	-4	0.03
PFNS	90	0.17	90	0.30	103	0.04	104	1.27	-24	0.02	-16	0.01
PFDS	90	0.32	82	0.26	102	0.22	95	0.89	-37	0.00	-24	0.02
PFDoDS	101	0.85	56	0.62	111	0.89	65	0.80	-68	0.02	-43	0.34
PFOcDA	224	0.87	36	1.10	246	0.91	41	0.04	-96	0.44	-76	0.14

Table C.2: Quality control parameters for 43 target compounds for the water samples. Absolute recoveries (AR), Relative recoveries (RR), Matrix effects (ME), and RSD values for each respective parameter

Compound	AR (%)	RSD	RR (%)	RSD	ME (%)	RSD
DecaS	62	0.17	81	0.16	-56	0.06
GenX	86	0.04	112	0.06	-19	0.05
PFPeA	66	0.24	88	0.24	-49	0.01
PFHxA	73	0.04	97	0.04	-14	0.05
4:2 FTS	73	0.20	95	0.21	35	0.07
7H-PFHpA	81	0.48	109	0.50	-99	0.28
NaDONA	81	0.03	108	0.03	-4	0.04
TriDeFHxSA	68	0.39	115	0.49	-57	0.23
PFOA	82	0.02	109	0.03	1	0.01
6:2 FTS	86	0.06	112	0.04	9	0.04
PFHpS	83	0.01	108	0.02	-2	0.00
PFNA	78	0.02	128	0.12	-8	0.01
P37DMOA	78	0.09	127	0.08	-3	0.03
PFOSA	59	0.14	95	0.16	26	0.02
PFOS	67	0.11	109	0.04	-11	0.01
MeFOSA	41	0.20	66	0.27	9	0.02
PFDA	63	0.11	102	0.05	-35	0.06
EtFOSA	35	0.25	58	0.30	17	0.02
EtFOSAA	35	0.27	57	0.33	13	0.01
8:2 FTS	59	0.21	94	0.08	20	0.12
9Cl-PF3ONS	57	0.21	92	0.07	2	0.01
FOSAA	41	0.28	67	0.30	20	0.04
PFUnA	39	0.21	63	0.09	9	0.01
MeFOSAA	32	0.30	51	0.29	23	0.05
EtFOSE	35	0.33	57	0.32	7	0.06
PFDoDA	25	0.21	41	0.19	15	0.01
MeFOSE	33	0.28	54	0.26	-37	0.08
10:2 FTS	29	0.24	48	0.25	22	0.05
PFTriDA	22	0.29	35	0.32	7	0.04
diSAMPAP	12	0.60	20	0.64	-21	0.47
PFTDA	18	0.36	28	0.37	3	0.03
PFHxDA	10	0.49	15	0.49	-5	0.09
PFBA	28	0.59	37	0.58	-57	0.32
PFBS	79	0.03	102	0.05	3	0.03
PFPeS	78	0.02	102	0.04	-16	0.01
PFHpA	79	0.03	105	0.02	31	0.01
PFHxS	83	0.02	107	0.04	-14	0.00
PFECHS	80	0.02	104	0.01	-4	0.02
PFNS	47	0.21	75	0.07	-4	0.01
PFDS	29	0.17	47	0.10	-6	0.02
SAMPAP	3	0.89	5	0.88	-51	0.06
PFDoDS	21	0.30	35	0.34	-9	0.02
PFOcDA	15	0.87	23	0.92		0.06

D Concentrations in textile samples

Table D.1: Concentrations (ng/g) of the recycled samples (labeled REC) for 15 target PFAS. Concentrations below LOD are excluded

	PFPea	PFHxA	4:2FTS	NaDONA	PFOA	PFHpS	PFNA	P37DMOA	PFOSA	MeFOSA	PFDA	EtFOSA	EtFOSAA	9CI-PF3ONS
REC_1														
REC_2	2.46													
REC_3														
REC_4					1.20									
REC_5	3.00					2.15		0.15			0.30			
REC_6		30.43												
REC_7									0.29					
REC_8					3.50		0.08							
REC_9					2.06		0.46				0.09		0.06	
REC_10						0.21	1.66							0.06
REC_11														
REC_12								0.05						
REC_13														
REC_14				0.04					3.16					0.14
REC_15		0.69							1.12					0.20
REC_16							0.98		0.61					
REC_17		2.58							0.51					0.09
REC_18		6.08												
REC_19														
REC_20					4.38		10.64	1.78	3.32		23.73			0.11
REC_21														
REC_22														
REC_23										0.69				
REC_24									0.64					
REC_25	0.67								0.36					
REC_26		4.35				0.17			1.00	0.04				
REC_27									0.60					
REC_28			0.19											
REC_29					3.40									
REC_30								0.04						
REC_31			32.73											
REC_32													0.79	
REC_33									0.21					
REC_34									0.39					
REC_35									0.26					
REC_36														
REC_37														

Table D.2: Concentrations (ng/g) of the post-consumer samples obtained from Fretex (labeled FX) for 15 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD are excluded

	PFPea	PFHxA	4:2 FTS	NaDONA	PFOA	PFHpS	PFNA	P37DMOA	PFOSA	PFOS	MeFOSA	PFDA	EtFOSA	EtFOSAA	9CI-PF3ONS
FX_1							0.58							0.14	0.09
FX_2					0.99	1.81			0.07	1.72	0.09			0.08	
FX_3															0.12
FX_4										0.75				0.08	
FX_5								0.26	0.11	1.00				0.10	0.07
FX_6										2.19					
FX_7										0.91				0.08	
FX_8					0.82		0.69	0.27						0.12	
FX_9					4.31		0.80			12.22					
FX_10					1.25					0.84					
FX_11										2.92					
FX_12										0.67				0.15	0.09
FX_13								0.09		1.03				0.08	
FX_14	32.53								0.16	0.45				0.12	
FX_15			0.54							1.19				0.04	
FX_16					6.12			0.15		0.47		0.74			
FX_17										0.75					
FX_18														0.15	0.12
FX_19					0.81							0.27			
FX_20		15.66				0.81		0.20		0.54					
FX_21									0.77					0.20	0.13
FX_22													0.04		
FX_23					2.56	9.59	0.24			0.29	0.22		0.28	0.06	0.07
FX_24		94.59					2.23				0.29			0.07	1.11
FX_25			0.23			0.37					0.08		0.37		
FX_26		3.73	21.13								0.04		0.48	0.21	
FX_27					4.35					5.24	0.42		0.57		
FX_28		54.15				0.11									
FX_29								0.07			0.22		0.31	0.06	0.11
FX_30															

Table D.3: Concentrations (ng/g) of the recycled samples (labeled REC) for 10 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD are excluded. This table also includes the occurrence of different PFAS in each sample, and the calculated total PFAS concentrations (ng/g)

	10:2 FTS	PFTriDa	PFTDA	PFBS	PFPeS	PFHpA	PFHxS	PFECHS	PFNS	PFDoDS	Occurrence	TOTAL ng/g
REC_1											2	2.71
REC_2										8.77	2	9.71
REC_3								0.08			1	0.08
REC_4				1.64					2.17		3	5.02
REC_5											6	10.49
REC_6										0.26	3	32.65
REC_7			4.39			0.80	0.37				4	5.86
REC_8						2.43					4	6.07
REC_9											3	2.61
REC_10						3.34					5	5.43
REC_11											0	0.00
REC_12											1	0.05
REC_13									0.34		4	22.63
REC_14											3	1.36
REC_15									0.32		4	2.60
REC_16											3	3.61
REC_17								0.12			2	2.70
REC_18											3	8.40
REC_19											1	0.52
REC_20		2.15	2.61			1.30					12	64.30
REC_21											2	22.89
REC_22											0	0.00
REC_23											1	0.69
REC_24											1	0.64
REC_25											4	5.54
REC_26								0.14		1.12	5	4.22
REC_27											1	0.60
REC_28	0.46					1.31		0.20		0.84	6	6.40
REC_29							0.62				1	0.62
REC_30				0.08	0.27		0.49				6	72.53
REC_31		2.53									4	23.94
REC_32								0.40		1.73	4	3.32
REC_33											1	0.26
REC_34									0.61		2	0.91
REC_35					0.66		0.33			14.84	3	15.84
REC_36					0.68			0.14			2	0.82
REC_37											0	0.00

Table D.4: Concentrations (ng/g) of the post-consumer samples obtained from Fretex (labelled FX) for 10 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD is excluded. This table also includes the occurrence of different PFAS in each sample, and the calculated total PFAS concentrations (ng/g)

	10:2 FTS	PFTriDa	PFTDA	PFBS	PFPeS	PFHpA	PFHxS	PFECHS	PFNS	PFDoDS	Occurrence	TOTAL ng/g
FX_1					0.16					13.70	5	14.68
FX_2			2.08								7	6.85
FX_3					1.76			0.17		11.12	4	13.17
FX_4											2	0.83
FX_5										11.96	6	13.49
FX_6					0.42			0.04		3.52	4	6.17
FX_7					2.79		0.79	0.07		17.81	6	22.44
FX_8										17.33	5	19.23
FX_9							2.01			7.02	5	26.35
FX_10						1.83				7.78	4	11.70
FX_11					0.49					2.63	3	6.04
FX_12										30.18	4	31.08
FX_13								0.21		22.17	5	23.58
FX_14							2.65			2.61	6	38.52
FX_15										36.13	4	37.90
FX_16							0.70				5	8.18
FX_17								0.03		5.01	3	5.79
FX_18					1.52					18.81	4	20.60
FX_19					0.23		0.36			11.63	5	13.29
FX_20										17.02	5	34.23
FX_21			1.67								4	2.77
FX_22					0.27					16.74	3	17.05
FX_23					0.43			0.13			10	13.88
FX_24											5	98.29
FX_25										15.55	5	16.59
FX_26					1.71			0.04		3.80	8	31.13
FX_27										13.69	5	24.27
FX_28							0.47			4.28	4	59.02
FX_29										19.41	6	20.18
FX_30							0.33	0.05		15.08	3	15.46

Table D.5: Concentrations (ng/cm²) of the purchased recycled samples (labeled REC) for 13 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD is excluded.

	DecaS	Gen X	PFPea	PFHxA	4:2 FTS	NaDONA	PFOA	PFHpS	PFNA	P37DMOA	PFOSA	PFOS	MeFOSA
REC_1				0.050								0.005	
REC_1												0.022	
REC_1							0.030						
REC_1			0.261						0.187		0.013	0.054	
REC_1	0.093			3.025									0.014
REC_1	1.370						0.337			0.008			
REC_1	0.852						0.091		0.021				
REC_1								0.006	0.049			0.005	
REC_1	0.006									0.001			
REC_1				0.199								0.033	
REC_1						0.001						0.034	
REC_1			0.022						0.031			0.019	
REC_1	0.009											0.027	
REC_1			0.024										0.013
REC_1			0.347										0.012
REC_1							0.071		0.172	0.029	0.054	0.022	

Table D.6: Concentrations (ng/cm²) of the post-consumer textiles obtained from Fretex (labeled FX) for 13 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD are excluded.

	DecaS	Gen X	PFPea	PFHxA	4:2 FTS	NaDONA	PFOA	PFHpS	PFNA	P37DMOA	PFOSA	PFOS	MeFOSA
FX_1													
FX_2							0.015	0.028			0.001	0.026	0.001
FX_3													
FX_4	0.003											0.013	
FX_5										0.007	0.003	0.027	
FX_6												0.125	
FX_7												0.031	
FX_8	0.036						0.041		0.034	0.013			
FX_9	0.025						0.418		0.078			1.187	
FX_10							0.022					0.015	
FX_11												0.099	
FX_12												0.021	
FX_13										0.002		0.027	
FX_14			0.941								0.005	0.013	
FX_15					0.019							0.041	
FX_16								0.122		0.003		0.009	
FX_17	0.004											0.017	
FX_18	0.013												
FX_19							0.016						
FX_20	0.005			0.306				0.016		0.004		0.011	
FX_21											0.014		
FX_22													
FX_23							0.063	0.234	0.006			0.007	0.005
FX_24				1.826					0.043				0.006
FX_25					0.005			0.008					0.002
FX_26	0.050			0.078	0.445								0.001
FX_27							0.411					0.494	0.040
FX_28				0.970				0.002					
FX_29										0.001			0.004
FX_30													

x

D CONCENTRATIONS IN TEXTILE SAMPLES

Table D.7: Concentrations (ng/cm²) of the purchased recycled samples (labeled REC) for 10 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD are excluded. This table also includes the calculated total PFAS concentrations (ng/cm²)

	PFDA	EtFOSA	EtFOSAA	9Cl-PF3ONS	PFUnA	PFDoDA	MeFOSE	PFTriDa	PFTDA	PFPeS	PFHpA	PFHxS	PFECHS	PFNS	PFDoDS	Total
REC_1																0.055
REC_1															0.203	0.225
REC_1												0.002				0.002
REC_1										0.041				0.055		0.126
REC_1	0.026					0.374										0.915
REC_1							0.195								0.026	3.338
REC_1								0.215			0.039	0.018				0.287
REC_1			0.006								0.234					1.954
REC_1	0.004															0.968
REC_1				0.002							0.100					0.162
REC_1																0.006
REC_1																0.001
REC_1				0.001										0.004		0.237
REC_1				0.006												0.042
REC_1														0.010		0.083
REC_1				0.005			0.160									0.201
REC_1												0.001				0.025
REC_1						0.120										0.480
REC_1																0.012
REC_1	0.384			0.002	0.076	0.133		0.035	0.042		0.021					1.041

Table D.8: Concentrations (ng/cm²) of the post-consumer samples obtained from Fretex (labeled FX) for 15 target compounds. Concentrations below LOD are excluded. This table also includes the calculated total PFAS concentrations (ng/cm²)

	PFDA	EtFOSA	EtFOSAA	9Cl-PF3ONS	PFUnA	PFDoDA	MeFOSE	PFTriDa	PFTDA	PFPeS	PFHpA	PFHxS	PFECHS	PFNS	PFDoDS	Total
FX_1		0.004	0.003						0.005					0.398	0.426	0.426
FX_2				0.001						0.032						0.105
FX_3					0.002						0.031			0.003		0.234
FX_4				0.001												0.017
FX_5				0.003	0.002											0.371
FX_6											0.024			0.002		0.352
FX_7				0.003							0.094		0.027	0.002		0.755
FX_8				0.006												0.994
FX_9													0.195			2.586
FX_10												0.032				0.208
FX_11											0.016					0.204
FX_12				0.005	0.003											0.997
FX_13				0.002										0.005		0.631
FX_14				0.003									0.077			1.114
FX_15				0.001												1.312
FX_16	0.015												0.014			0.163
FX_17														0.001		0.132
FX_18				0.003	0.002						0.030					0.419
FX_19			0.005								0.005		0.007			0.262
FX_20																0.673
FX_21				0.004	0.002					0.031						0.051
FX_22			0.001								0.006					0.379
FX_23			0.007	0.001	0.002						0.010			0.003		0.339
FX_24				0.001	0.021											1.897
FX_25			0.008													0.363
FX_26			0.010	0.004							0.036			0.001		0.705
FX_27			0.054													2.289
FX_28													0.009			1.057
FX_29			0.005	0.001	0.002											0.318
FX_30													0.009	0.001		0.434

Norwegian University of
Science and Technology